

**EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION
ON MARKET VALUE OF QUOTED MANUFACTURING
COMPANIES IN NIGERIA**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17235557>

Keywords:
Accounting
Information
[Net Asset
(NA) and Cash
Flow (CF)],
Market Value
and Quoted
Manufacturing
Companies.

Abstract: *The study was carried out to examine the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This study will ascertain the direction of the variables of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Ex-post facto design was adopted in the study because it required secondary data. Accounting information (independent variable) was represented by Net Asset (NA) and Cash Flow (CF). The dependent variable was Market Value (MV) while Revenue (REV) and Total Equity (TE) were the control variables chosen for the study. The population of the study was Thirty-one (31) manufacturing companies whose shares were traded on Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31st October 2024. Twenty-four (24) companies were selected as sample size for the study on the basis of availability of published financial statements with essential variables. Panel data required were collected from the sampled companies for the period of 2013 to 2023. Descriptive statistics and pooled panel linear regression statistical tools were used to analyze the data collected for the study. The results of the analysis revealed that NA and CF had positive and significant influence on MV of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. From the findings, the researcher concluded that accounting information had positive and significant influence on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It was recommended that the managers of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria should accumulate and acquire more of non-current assets to improve upon the market value of the entities. Also, sound and stringent accounting policies should be adopted in*

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajfir/index.php/ajfir/index>

order to ensure continuous improvement in cash flow of revenue into the entities for the purpose of achieving positive net cash flows that will raise the market value of the firms.

1 Introduction

The managers, being the agents in companies, are primarily expected to furnish the shareholders with adequate and relevant information about their operations and these are often prepared and presented in the form of published financial reports annually. The reports of operations or performance are contained in the statements which are made up of various elements, components and transactions. These financial statements provide information to different stakeholders as well as potential investors. The financial statements are conventionally made up of statement of financial position, statement of profit or loss account, statement of cash flow and statement of change in equity. Each of these statements contain sub-components namely, revenue, expenses, equity, assets and liabilities.

These five elements of financial statements are with essential attributes that could also help in providing meaningful information to users. The revenue status of a quoted company is capable of attracting or discouraging the interest of the potential investors. For instance, when a quoted company generate larger revenue in different accounting periods continuously and increasingly, a potential investor might be interested in such company. When costs and expenses are effectively managed and reduced

continuously in different accounting periods, its profit is certain that the stakeholders' wealth is maximized and potential investors would be attracted to the operation of such company.

When profitability is growing every year and larger proportion of retention of the profits is made for total equity to grow by the directors, the wealth of the owners is maximised where the stock price of such company might be increased correspondently. When total liabilities or debts are effectively managed to reduce financial risk in a quoted entity by the managers/directors, it is certain that the wealth of the shareholders might be maximized through improvement in the stock price of the company. When the composition of assets accumulated is with greater proportion of non-current assets to generate more revenue for the growth of the entity, potential investors might want to patronise such company (Mulenga, 2015). The service potential of the non-current assets to the revenue generation of the company is higher when the right and quality assets are put in place. This will help to enhance the market value of the entity. Other attributes of financial statements reported under the elements of financial statements could also provide essential information to users and these include net asset, cash flow, leverage, retained earnings and dividend payment.

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In contemporary time, accounting information is crucial to managers and other users of financial statements because the expectation of any kind of investment is to maximize returns. Accounting information affects all aspects of organization because it involves the utilization of available resources with the expectation of generating maximum returns or profits. Therefore, accounting information is described as information presented on published financial statements of quoted companies in different accounting periods. The various attributes that represent accounting information of quoted companies are capable of influencing market value of the entities at any time depending on the level of performance or efficiency of strategies and policies implemented by the managers (Kousenidis *et al.*, 2012).

The influence of all the attributes of accounting information on market value of quoted companies might either be positively or negatively felt depending on the operations carried out from which the outcomes are reported on financial statements. Market value is described as the level of improvement in shareholders' wealth. The market value indicators include stock price, market capitalization, market value of equity and price earnings ratio. The various indicators of market value are often influenced by the book value of items reported on financial statements which mainly include net asset and cash flow.

Studies have been conducted in this area of interest both locally and internationally but it appears that the empirical results presented by previous studies are inconclusive based on the variables and the time frame of these studies. In quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, the empirical investigation of the variables of accounting information on market value of the entities might bring about improvement in the general operations of the companies through effective review and adjustment of policies that have been adopted over the years.

The growth of quoted companies in different countries of the world solely depends on accounting information reported for past operations carried out. Studies in this area of interest have been conducted with the use of accounting ratios such as the investment ratios like earnings per share, dividend per share and price earnings ratio to represent accounting information (Shamki, 2012; Irsath *et al.*, 2015; Rahman and Liu, 2021). Market value in previous studies was mostly represented by closing stock price, average stock price and the model of Tobin's Q without the use of indicator like market capitalization to represent the market value. The use of predictors such as net asset and cash flow to represent accounting information in empirical studies are limited in the literature. In Nigeria, studies in this area were mostly on the use of investment ratios such as earnings per share, dividend per share, dividend payout ratio and price earnings ratio to

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represent accounting information where stock price was used mostly to represent market value. The empirical results of these studies in the extant literature of accounting have conflicting results depending on the sector used and the time frame selected for the studies. In most of the previous studies conducted, the selection of the time frame where significant changes have taken place on the published financial statements were not taken into consideration.

Quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria have limited studies especially with the use of variables such as net asset and cash flow to establish the influence on market value. On this note, it could be said that there are inadequate and inconclusive studies conducted in Nigeria on accounting information and market value of quoted companies. Thus, an attribute of accounting information is expected to influence the stock price of companies either positively or negatively because the level of performance achieved by managers is expected to have significant connection with the variables of shareholders' wealth (Shamki, 2012; Umoren *et al.*, 2018). An observation of some selected financial statements of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria shows that items of financial statements such as net asset and cash flow have been accumulated largely and increasingly in different accounting period but the stock price of these companies, which is a factor of market value, does not improve significantly in line with the trend of the items of

transactions reported. It seems the items of financial statements regarded as the attributes of accounting information do not really influence the market value of these entities. On this note, the empirical investigation of influence of the attributes of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria is fundamentally critical to be established from the period of 2013 to 2023.

The main objective of the study was to examine the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the influence of net asset on market capitalization of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
- ii. Assess the influence of cash flow on market capitalization of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
- iii. Evaluate the combined influence of net asset and cash flow on market capitalization of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

2 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Accounting Information

Accounting information is defined as the information derived from items of transaction or elements of financial statements reported by quoted companies to enable users to take effective decisions. It is also described as critical information for managerial decision in quoted

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companies. The roles played by accounting in business organizations for the purpose of providing accurate records about the past events that are critical for decision to be made, for correction of deviation and improvement in the wealth of shareholders (Sukmadilaga *et al.*, 2023). When talking about accounting information, there are two critical terms to be considered which are accounting and information. Accounting is perceived to be the systematic process of recording historical events expressed in monetary terms for the purpose of providing useful information that could guide the continuous operation of the organization (Abazu and Onuora, 2023; Závodný and Procházka, 2023). The provision of historical data about various transactions of quoted companies is made possible through accounting. On this note, it could be said that accounting is aimed at providing information for various users which are broadly classified into internal and external users (Kousenidis *et al.*, 2012). In other words, one could describe accounting as information generating mechanism or activities performed by set of individuals that have been trained in the field professionally to record, analyse and interpret transactions (Irsath *et al.*, 2015).

Accounting is also described as the systematic process of collecting, recording, classifying, interpreting financial data to arrive at useful information for the managers and other users of accounting information for decision purposes

(Rahman and Liu, 2021). In all the definitions of accounting, the ultimate expectation is always to arrive at information for sound decision to be made in an organization. Thus, accounting is seen as a lifeblood of modern organizations because without proper and accurate records maintained in an organization, future operation of such organization might not be assured. The going concern status of any organization solely rely on the effectiveness of the recording processes maintained in an organization which incorporates the internal control system. This simply means that in an organization where professional and experienced accountants are not involved, the going concern status of such company might be threatened as the information generated by accounting activities is so crucial for future decision-making and for the assurance of continuous operation of the company. When talking about accounting in this situation, the various items reported on the financial statements are critical factors that help to provide information to managers and other stakeholders of organization.

Accounting information is described as the information presented on financial statements published by quoted companies in an accounting period (Omokhudu and Ibadin, 2015). The various items of transactions reported in an accounting period are usually regarded as those factors of accounting information. This is because for a potential investor to take decision whether to invest in a

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quoted company or not, the historical information presented on financial statements are crucial such as revenue position, assets accumulated, the proportion of non-current asset acquired, the level of profit made, the level of liabilities accumulated, the cash flow position and the current stock price in the market (Umoren *et al.*, 2018). These are yardsticks of decisions derived from financial statements made available by accounting information. In this case, it could be said that accounting information is information derived for decision purpose from items of transactions reported historically as a result of past events which could also affect future activities of an organization (Karğın, 2013).

2.1.2 Users of Accounting Information

Users of accounting information are broadly classified into two regarded as internal and external users of accounting information. These are discussed accordingly:

i. Internal Users of Accounting Information: These are users of accounting information that are part and parcel of the operations of organization (Edet and Umoh, 2024). They are described as stakeholders that often take part in the daily operational activities of quoted companies in accordance with the accounting policies of the organization (Kwon, 2018). The stakeholders that constitute the internal users of accounting information individually have diverse interests or stakes in the operation of companies. It is the diverse

interests of these individuals regarded as internal users of accounting information that often make them to be more concerned about the operations carried in organization (Khomidah and Setiawan, 2022). The fundamental internal users of accounting information are managers and employees. The managers, also known as directors, are those individuals that formulate and implemented both accounting policies and strategies for the progress or growth of organization. The level of progress attained by a quoted company is usually attributed to the effectiveness of policies and strategies implemented by the managers (Omokhudu and Ibadin, 2015).

The managers/directors are always expected to carried their responsibilities in accordance with the interest of the owners or equity shareholders (Ihenyen and Asemota, 2024). This simply means that the policies and strategies implemented by the managers should be in line with the interest of the owners and not based on personal interest of the managers/directors (Mulenga, 2015). The main interest of managers, as internal users of accounting information, is on the monthly remuneration and other incentives often granted to them for job performance as reward to encourage the performance. Managers are often paid monthly salaries for the services rendered based on the companies' policies for salaries. Managers are usually interested on published financial statements of their companies for purpose of

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evaluating their performance in terms of the policies and strategies formulated and implemented in the past accounting period (Rahman and Sharma, 2020). Evaluation of published financial statements helps the managers to either review their strategies and policies implemented or to continuously implement the existing policies and strategies (Etim *et al.*, 2022).

Employees are internal users that are mostly concerned about their job security as well as their monthly remuneration (Rahman and Liu, 2021). They are internal users of accounting information that often take part in daily activities of organization with the anticipation of getting monthly remuneration from the organization. They often use financial statements published by management of quoted companies to assess the possibility the organization will be in existence for them to have their remuneration continuously to enable them meet up with their daily commitments in their household (Tarik, 2021).

ii. External Users of Accounting Information: External users of accounting information are set of individuals or corporate bodies that do not take part in the daily operation of an organization but are interested in the level of performance or growth of the company (Der *et al.*, 2016). This simply means that the external users of accounting information are individuals that are outside the operations of quoted companies but are often

interested on the published financial statements of the quoted entities for directing their decisions about investment and their returns (Sukmadilaga *et al.*, 2023). External users are mostly interested in the published financial statements often prepared and presented by management of quoted companies for the purpose of formulating sound decisions (Shamki, 2012). Those that constitute the external users of accounting information include shareholders, debt holders, customers, suppliers, government, financial analyst and regulatory authorities (Rahman and Liu, 2021). Shareholders include both potential and existing individuals in quoted companies.

For the existing shareholders they are interested in the published financial statements of their companies to be able to understand the level of growth attained by managers through the implementation of policies and strategies and with the use of their funds to maximize their interests (Itan and Riana, 2021). For the potential shareholders, they are interested in the published financial statements of quoted companies to evaluate viable opportunities in which they could invest their surplus funds (Chehade and Prochazka, 2022). Debt holders are stakeholders that grant loans to quoted companies and they are also seen as investors because they often expect a certain reward regarded as interest usually expressed in percentage on the face value of the debt instrument (Endri and Fathony, 2020). Debt

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holders are both existing and potential. For the existing debt holders, they are interested in published financial statements of quoted companies to assess the possibility in which they could get their annual interest income as agreed on the debt agreement as well as the principal amount at maturity (Harvest *et al.*, 2022).

For the potential debt holders, they are interested in published financial statements of quoted companies to evaluate the opportunities and the possibilities in which they could grant loans to those companies that approach them for the facilities. Customers are interested in published financial statements of quoted companies to fundamentally understand the possibility in which the entities will continue to produce and offer products or services to the markets by maintaining all manner of quality as stable organization (Ihenyen and Asemota, 2024). Suppliers are stakeholders who often assess the published financial statements of quoted companies to fundamentally understand the possibility in which those companies could honour their obligations when due or the possibility in which they could grant further credit of inputs or sale on account to those firms (Abughniem *et al.*, 2020). Government is interested on published financial statements of quoted companies for income tax purpose. This is because quoted companies in an economy are expected to pay their taxes from the profits declared at the end of accounting periods (Ajape *et al.*, 2018).

Government is also interested in the published financial statements of quoted companies to review the extent to which the companies have complied with relevant regulation in the economy as well as international accounting standards (Al-Slehat, 2020). Financial analysts are interested in financial statements to evaluate the level of performance achieved by companies for some years as well as predicting the financial status of the companies in future. Regulatory authorities are external users of accounting information because the assessment of compliance of those companies on the laws and regulations is usually done on the annual reports of quoted companies (Altahtamouni, 2018). The regulatory agencies include Security and Exchange Commission (SEC), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN), among others.

2.1.3 Variables of Accounting Information

Fundamentally, there are essential variables or factors that could represent accounting information in accordance with the idea of published financial statements of quoted companies (Der *et al.*, 2016). In other words, the items of transactions reported on financial statements are regarded as attributes of accounting information as each of these indicators is capable of providing information to stakeholders or owners of companies (Tarik, 2021). The various indicators of accounting information include the following:

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i. Net Asset: Net asset is a fundamental factor of accounting information that usually represents the extent to which managers of quoted companies have invested the available funds sourced from both debt and equity to grow the firms for the owners. Net asset is often computed as the difference between total assets less current liabilities in an accounting period for a quoted company (Anuar *et al.*, 2021). The key determinants of the magnitude of net asset are the level of total assets and current liabilities in an accounting period. In a generic situation, when net asset is large, it could be said that the managers of such company are more concerned in utilizing less or minimal current liabilities or short-term debt in carrying out the operations of the entity (Edet and Umoh, 2024). On the other hand, when net asset is minimal, it could be said that the managers of such firm have accumulated less non-current asset and more of current liabilities greater than current assets in the accounting period (Charlie and Edet, 2023). Larger net asset is capable of attracting the interest of potential investors because it could be viewed as a company that has less short-term financial obligations and with the larger asset portfolio, the reputation of the company in the market is assured (Davies and Macfubara, 2018). Net asset is capable of influencing market value in the situation where the magnitude of the net asset is large as the potential equity shareholders would want to acquire shares in such company and in such a situation, the price

of the stock will be raised (Charlie and Edet, 2023 and Edet and Umoh, 2024). The focus of the researcher in this study is to investigate the direction of net asset, being an attribute of accounting information, on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

ii. Cash Flow: Cash flow is described as the level of revenue generated in cash and cash equivalent and payment made in cash as well in an accounting period (Itan and Riana, 2021). When talking about cash flows, the two critical things that run through the mind of an individual especially an accountant is that the level of inflows and outflows generated and paid respectively is what is being mentioned (Ni *et al.*, 2019). Also, when talking about cash flows, it is often said to be the net of cash revenue generated and expenses paid by a quoted company in an accounting period (Chabachib *et al.*, 2020). Cash flow is seen as a critical or essential item of transactions reported basically in three components of statement of cash flows such as operating activities, investing activities and financing activities (Edet and Umoh, 2024). The cash flow of an entity is derived from the three components of a financial statement regarded as statement of cash flows. Cash flow from operating activities is simply regarded as the inflows and outflows of cash from the conduct of the principal activities of a quoted company (Yusuf *et al.*, 2021).

Cash flow is seen as a fundamental factor of accounting information because it reveals the

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strength of a quoted company in a short-term to handle obligation or commitment (Itan and Riana, 2021). Potential investors are interested in positive cash flows in different accounting periods for a quoted company because the life blood of any business is cash and insufficient cash is capable of reducing the reputation of a quoted firm as well as influencing the market value of the company negatively (Camodeca *et al.*, 2014). It is on this note that the influence of cash flow, being a factor of accounting information, is investigated on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

iii. Total Equity: Equity is simply regarded as the interest of owners in business organization (Edet and Umoh, 2024). Ownership of quoted companies comes from the acquisition of equity shares advertised by listed companies. The capital provided by the equity shareholders with other components that indicates their stakes constitute total equity (Buzinskiene and Rudyte, 2021). In other words, total equity is simply regarded as the aggregate of share capital, share premium, retained earnings and other components of equity (Edet and Umoh, 2024). Equity capital is often reported on the financial statement called statement of change in equity. In quoted companies, equity capital is regarded as a very important source of funding the acquisition of assets (Edet and Umoh, 2024). The basic components that make up total equity as stated earlier are share capital, share premium and

retained earnings. The aggregate of the components of equity and total debt is equal total assets, and this is one aspect of accounting equation especially when preparing statement of financial position (Anuar *et al.*, 2021).

Total equity is capable of influencing market value either positively or negatively depending on the composition (Bui and Pham, 2023). In this case, total equity could represent accounting information because the status of total equity in a quoted company is capable of providing information not just to the existing shareholders but to the potential investors. In this case, it could be said that the attribute could influence both other factors of accounting information such as net asset and cash flow as well as the indicator of market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

iv. Revenue: Revenue is described as the income made through the sales of products manufactured by a company. It could also be described as income generated in normal business operation of a quoted company (Irsath *et al.*, 2015 and Bawa, 2022). Revenue is an accounting factor that influences other attributes such as profitability, total equity and cash flows. In every accounting period, managers of quoted companies usually anticipate larger revenue to be realised and this is why meaningful policies are formulated from the implemented strategies to improve upon the revenue. In the activities of quoted companies, what constitutes revenue is simply regarded as

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the income generated from the principal activities of the entities such as the sales of products manufactured by the companies or income from services rendered by the entities to individuals or other corporate entities (Rahman and Liu, 2021). Revenue is capable of influencing market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria either positively or negatively. Thus, the direction of these attributes on market value is essential precisely in this study.

2.1.4 Market Value

The owners of companies who are shareholders are always interested about the maximization of their wealth through the growth of their shares in terms of stock price. Market value is an interesting indicator that shows the level of growth or improvement attained by a quoted company at a given time (Kwon, 2018). The continuous improvement or improve in stock price of shares could be seen as an advantage to the existing shareholders as this usually help to generate more wealth as well as attracting the interest of the potential investors (Uwuigbe *et al.*, 2016). Although, as the stock price continues to increase potential investor might find it difficult to acquire the shares of the company as the unit of shares is costly but for the existing shareholders, their wealth is maximized. For the fact that quoted companies are not run and managed by the shareholders or the owners but by the agents who are the directors with adequate business experience, it is possible to

say that those directors have greater responsibilities to ensure that market value of their entities is improved meaningfully in different accounting period (Austine *et al.*, 2014).

The process of ensuring that the market value of quoted company is improved is by formulating and implementing policies and strategies that have meaningful effect on the key attributes of financial statements or elements of financial statements such as revenue, assets, equity and liabilities (Vijitha and Nimalathan, 2014). To improve upon the revenue of a quoted company could also bring about maximization of profitability as well as growth in total equity as retention of profit is directly influenced by the level of profit made in an accounting period (Chan *et al.*, 2022). Also, when profit is maximized, it is possible to say that the interest of the potential investors might be attracted where the stock price will be raised and as stock price is raised, the market value of the company is also improved (Chehade and Prochazka, 2022). Accumulation of assets in quoted companies is also crucial to the improvement in market value. This is because potential shareholders or investors are interested in the asset base of quoted entities reported historically for the purpose of decision making. The components of total assets are usually split where their expectation is often placed on the level of non-current assets maintained by the quoted entities.

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Market capitalization is seen as another indicator of market value that is usually computed by the products of stock price and equity shares outstanding at a given accounting period (Nwaobia *et al.*, 2016; Ogbodo and Osioma, 2020). It is also viewed as the market value of equity, debt and other components of long-term financing instruments (Al-Slehat, 2020). Because of the fact that data on market value of debt and other long-term financing instruments are not always available and the computations are also difficult, thus, the focus of market capitalization in this study is on the equity component regarded as share capital. The total equity shares outstanding is derived as share capital reported on statements of financial position divided by the nominal value of ₦0.5. The larger the market capitalization, the larger the market value and the lower the market capitalization, the lower the market value of a quoted company (Altahtamouni, 2018 and Umoren *et al.*, 2018). The key determinants of market capitalization are the level of stock price and equity shares outstanding. When the stock price is high in a given accounting period with an existing equity share outstanding, market capitalization is certain to be maximised in the accounting period (Omokhudu and Ibadin, 2015). When the stock price of a company is lower, the market capitalization will not be maximized with an existing equity share outstanding.

This is similar to equity share outstanding in any accounting period. When both stock price and equity share outstanding increase in an accounting period, larger market capitalization is certain to be realised (Ihenyen and Asemota, 2024). Market capitalization is a good indicator of market value especially when the predictors are not expressed in ratios or in percentage. In this case, market capitalization is a good representation of market value in this study to assess the influence of accounting information using net asset and cash flow as essential predictors on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

2.1.5 Nexus Between Accounting Information and Market Value

Accounting information and market value of quoted entities is an interesting area of research that cuts across various aspects of elements of financial statements (Ajape *et al.*, 2018). The connection between the attributes of financial statements and factors of market value is usually expected because the efficiency of managers is reflected on the reported items of transactions on financial statements, and they are expected to influence market value as well (Shamki, 2012 and Abughniem *et al.*, 2020). Thus, an attribute of accounting information is expected to influence the stock price of companies either positively or negatively because the level of performance achieved by managers is expected to have significant connection with the variables of shareholders' wealth (Umoren *et al.*, 2018).

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajfir/index.php/ajfir/index>

An observation of some selected financial statements of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria shows that items of financial statements such as net asset and cash flow have been accumulated largely and increasingly in different accounting period but the stock price of these companies, which is a factor of market value, does not improve significantly in line with the trend of the items of transactions reported. It seems the items of financial statements regarded as the attributes of accounting information do not really influence the market value of these entities. On this note, the empirical investigation of influence of the attributes of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria is fundamentally critical to be established from the period of 2013 to 2023.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Signalling Theory

Signalling theory was formulated and advanced by Spence in 1973 based on his observation on some attributes which he believed to provide signals for essential information. Based on the perspective of the author, certain attributes are indicators that could help to provide information for effective decision making and it is always expected that the parameters or indicators are provided at any time before decision is taken. The author of the theory also made it clear that it is important to understand different signals for decision making at any time. This is because there could be different signals

pointing at different information which means that adequate understanding of such signals might help in effective decision making. Financial statements usually prepared and published by managers/directors of quoted companies are always with several items of transactions that are regarded as sources of information to the investors or stakeholders. The classification of various components of financial statements into the respective elements such as revenue, expenses, assets, equity and liabilities could also help to provide information for decision making at any time.

According to Spence (1973), the magnitude of items of transactions presented at the end of an accounting period for a quoted company might be a signal to vital information. This simply means that signalling theory is related to accounting information as the various items of transactions reported on financial statements such as net asset and cash flow are signals of essential information to investors which could also influence the wealth of the shareholders or market value of the entity. Larger net asset reported at the end of accounting period for a quoted company in different accounting period with greater proportion of non-current assets indicates that the entity is a large firm which will always generate adequate revenue and maximize the wealth of the shareholders (Etim *et al.*, 2022). With the large net asset base recorded by a quoted entity in different accounting period investors (both potential) will

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classify such firm as one that will always report larger revenue, profit, total equity as well as paying larger amount of dividends to the shareholders at the end of every accounting period. Such company will always provide information to the debt holders in terms of paying back the interest of the debts annually and the principal at maturity.

Cash flow is another fundamental attribute of accounting information that helps existing investors to have confidence on the operation of a quoted company especially when positive and large amount of net cash flows from the three components is reported in different accounting period for the firm (Hafiz *et al.*, 2022). In other words, it could be viewed that for firm with positive cash flow balance in different accounting periods, short-term obligations will always be honoured without any default and the reputation of the company will continue to be improved in the markets. Positive net cash flow balance is regarded as signal that could help the potential investors to decide to acquire the shares of a firm with such balance or grant loans to the company with the expectation of recovering both annual interest and principal amount at maturity (Khomidah and Setiawan, 2022). A quoted company with negative net cash flow balance in different accounting periods might discourage both the existing and the potential investors because the balance of the cash flow is a signal to the investors that such

company might not be able to honour their obligations when the need arises in future.

Based on the discussion and in accordance with signalling theory, it could be said that the various attributes of accounting information are signals to investors and the magnitude of items of transactions reported at the end of operation are crucial factors that could influence the wealth of the shareholders either positively or negatively. In this case, net asset and cash flow are signals of accounting information that provide information to potential and existing investors which might also influence market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria either positively or negatively. The assertion in this study is that signalling theory is related as the performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria reported on financial statements annually is with signals for decision making which could in turn maximize the wealth of the shareholders in terms of improvement in stock price and growth in market capitalization. In this case, the theory was adopted in this study.

2.3 Empirical Review

Vijitha and Nimalathan (2014) examined the value relevance of accounting information and share price: A study of listed manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka. The study covered the period from 2007 to 2011. The accounting information used in this study were earnings per share (EPS), net assets value per share (NAVPS) and return on equity (ROE). Also, price earnings

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ratio to share price to share price. Relevant data were sourced from the published annual reports and financial statements of the manufacturing firms listed in CSE in Sri Lanka. The data were analysed using multiple regression technique and the result showed that there was a significant impact of accounting information on the share price. The result also indicated a significant correlation between value relevance of accounting information and share price.

Nwaobia *et al.* (2016) examined value relevance of accounting information and firm value: A study of consumer goods manufacturing sector in Nigeria. The aim of the study was to examine empirically the importance and influence of accounting information on firm value of listed consumer goods manufacturing sector in Nigeria. The relevant variables of the study were relevant of accounting information (independent variable) measured by earnings per share (EPS), book value per share (BVPS), dividend per share (DPS), liquidity (LQ) and cash flow from operations (CFOP) and market value of equity (dependent variable). Quantitative research design approach was employed by the researchers. The study sampled twenty-eight (28) consumer goods listed firms listed on Nigerian Stock Exchange. Panel data were collected from the published annual reports and financial statements of the sampled firms listed in NSE. Multiple regression technique was used to analyse the obtained data. The result revealed that there was no influence

of accounting information on firm value before the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs). Thus, the researchers concluded that change in standards from SAS to IFRSs had no significant influence on the accounting information as a predictor of firm's value.

Tarik (2021) conducted a study on the value relevance of accounting information and its impact on stock prices: A study on listed pharmaceutical companies at Dhaka stock exchange of Bangladesh. The variables used for the study were EPS, net operating cash flow per share, net asset value per share, cash dividend per share, and stock dividend per share and market value per share. The period of the study covered 2017 to 2019. Relevant data in relative to the variables of the study were retrieved from the published annual reports and financial statements of the pharmaceutical companies in DSE sampled for the study. The results of the analysis ascertained that there was a statistical positive and significant relationship of net operating cash flow per share, net assets value per share with market value per share. On the other hand, showed that there was negative and significant influence of EPS on market value per share. The outcomes of the analysis also indicated that cash dividend per share and stock dividend per share had positive and inconsequential relationship with market value per share.

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Chegade and Prochazka (2022) investigated value relevance of accounting information in an emerging market: The case of IFRS adoption by non-financial listed firms in Saudi Arabia. The study aimed at examining value relevance of accounting information in an emerging market. The study was conducted to cover the period from 2014 to 2019 and ninety-eight (98) non-financial quoted entities in Saudi Arabia were used for the study. The dependent variable of the study was market value per share while the independent variables were book value per share (BVPS), earnings per share (EPS) and operating cash flow per share (OCFPS). The control variables selected by the researchers were dividend pay-out ratio (DPR), leverage (LV) and industry type (IT). A dummy variable of IFRSs adoption was used in the study. Panel data were collected from the financial statements of the sampled entities. Data were analysed by descriptive statistics and panel regression approach. From the analysis, it was observed that the variables that represented value relevance of accounting information all exerted positive and significant influence on the market value per share of the non-financial entities quoted in Saudi Arabia.

Etim *et al.* (2022) assessed value relevance of accounting information and share prices movement of quoted consumer and industrial goods in Nigeria. The intention of the researchers was to evaluate the influence of value relevance of accounting information on

share prices of quoted consumer and industrial goods in Nigeria. The variables that represented value relevance of accounting information in the study were book value per share (BVPS), earnings per share (EPS) and cash flow from operating activities (CFO). Quoted consumer goods and industrial goods entities were studied separately. The data in accordance with the variables of the study were extracted from the financial statements of the entities sample for the study from the period of 2015 to 2021. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics and linear regression approach. From the analysis, it was observed that BVPS exerted negative and insignificant influence on stock price and CFO and EPS exerted positive and insignificant influence on stock price of consumer goods entities in Nigeria. It was also found that BVPS exerted positive and insignificant influence on stock price, CFO showed negative and insignificant influence on stock price and EPS indicated positive and consequential influence on stock price of quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

Khomidah and Setiawan (2022) conducted a study on value relevance of accounting information: Evidence from banking industry in ASEAN. The aim of the study was to examine the influence of value relevance of accounting information on stock price of banking industry in ASEAN. The researchers covered the period of 2017 to 2019 in the study and value relevance of accounting information was represented by

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earnings per share (EPS), book value per share (BVPS), company age (CA), company size (CS) and debt-to-equity ratio (DER). Control variable used in the study was gross domestic product (GDP) and essential data collected for the study were analysed by descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression approach. The analysis revealed that EPS exerted direct and significant influence on stock price while CA and CS exerted adverse and insignificant influence on stock price of the entities studied. It was also found that DER exerted positive and insignificant influence on stock price of the firms studied. GDP had a positive and significant influence on stock price of the companies.

Abazu and Onuora (2023) examined accounting information and stock price volatility of quoted consumer firms in Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to ascertain the influence of accounting information on stock price volatility of quoted consumer firms in Nigeria. Twenty-six (26) consumer goods entities quoted in Nigeria were sampled for the study and the study covered the period of 2012 to 2021. Accounting information was represented by dividend pay-out ratio (DPR), dividend per share (DPS), dividend yield ratio (DYR) and retained earnings per share (REPS). The essential data for the study were collected from the financial statements of the entities studied. Essential data collected in line with the variables of the study were analysed by descriptive statistics and

ordinary least square (OLS) regression approach. From the analysis, it was observed that DPS and DYR exerted positive and inconsequential influence on stock price volatility while REPS and DPR had positive and material influence on stock price volatility of the quoted companies studied.

Sukmadilaga *et al.* (2023) conducted a study on can accounting value relevance and pricing error influence stock price of high-technology service enterprises? The intention of the researchers was to investigate the influence of accounting value relevance on stock price of high-technology service enterprises. Three hundred and twenty-six (326) technological service enterprises were adopted as the sample size of the study and the key variables that represented accounting value relevance were diluted earnings per share (DEPS), revenue per share (RPS) and book value per share (BVPS). Secondary data were collected from the financial statements of the sampled entities. The data were analysed by descriptive statistics and ordinary least square (OLS) approach. From the analysis, the results showed that DEPS and BVPS exerted positive and significant influence on stock price of the companies while RPS exerted positive and insignificant influence on stock price of the companies studied.

Závodný and Procházka (2023) examined IFRS adoption and value relevance of accounting information in the V4 region. The aim of the study was to evaluate IFRS adoption and value

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relevance of accounting information on share price. The researchers covered the period of 2005 to 2017 and the key variables that represented value relevance of accounting information were earnings per share (EPS), book value per share (BVPS) and cash flow from operating activities per share (CFOPS). Data for the study were collected from the audited financial statements of the companies. The analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics and panel regression statistical tool. From the analysis, it was observed that all the variables of value relevance of accounting information (EPS, BVPS and CFOPS) showed positive and significant influence on stock price of the companies studied.

Ihenyen and Asemota (2024) investigated the effect of accounting information on stock price of listed consumer goods company in Nigeria. The study was conducted to assess the influence of accounting information on stock price of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The study covered the period from 2010 to 2023 and ten (10) consumer goods companies in Nigeria were selected for the study. Accounting information, being the independent information was proxied by book value (BV) and cash flow ratio (CFR) while the dependent variable chosen for the study was stock price. The data for the study were obtained from financial reports of the companies selected for the study and the data were analysed using descriptive statistics and linear regression techniques. The result of

the analysis showed that BV and CFR had a material influence on stock price.

2.3.1 Gap in Empirical Literature

Accounting information and market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria is an interesting area of research based on the variables used in this study. Several studies have been conducted both locally and internationally in this area of interest but it seems the empirical results derived from previous studies are inconclusive because of the area of the study, the sectors studied, the time frame for the study and the measurement of the variables. In the area of the study, several studies in this area were conducted in foreign countries other than Nigeria. Several studies in this area of interest conducted internationally with the use of essential variables of accounting information such as net asset and cash flow are mostly in quoted manufacturing companies but in Nigeria limited studies were conducted in this area of interest in accordance with the key variables of accounting information such as net asset, cash flow, profitability and leverage. The time frame mostly used in the previous studies are the combination of pre-adoption and post-adoption periods of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs).

The measurement of the variables of accounting information mostly used in previous studies is in ratios with various limitations in interpretations. The measurement of market value in previous studies is mostly the model of

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Tobin's Q, stock price and price-to-book ratio. In the present study, quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, which made up of quoted consumer goods and industrial goods entities, are used. In this study, the post adoption period of IFRSs is strictly considered from 2013 to 2023. The measurement of market value adopted is market capitalization and the representation of accounting information such as net asset and cash flow was not in ratios as in the previous studies. Variables such as net asset and cash flow were rarely used in the previous studies in Nigeria which has to do with the influence of accounting information on market value of companies. Thus, the establishment of the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria with the use of the key variables such as net asset and cash flow on market capitalization from the period of 2013 to 2023 would contribute to the extant literature and add to the stock of knowledge. Hence, the need for the present study.

3 Methodology

The *ex-post facto* research design method was adopted in this study because the study used secondary data collected from financial statements of the sampled quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The adoption of this research design enabled the researcher to examine the influence of variables of accounting information and market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The decision affords the researcher opportunity of not being able to manipulate the data.

The population of the study was made up of all quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria whose stocks were traded on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group. The quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria as at 31st October, 2024 were thirty-one (31) considered by the researcher in this study as the population. For this reason, the population of this study was thirty-one (31) quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The sample size of this study was drawn from the aggregate population of thirty-one (31) quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria on the floor of NGX. Twenty-four (24) quoted manufacturing companies were drawn and sampled for the study from the sub-sectors of consumer goods and industrial goods entities in Nigeria considered in the study. The quoted manufacturing companies used as the sample size were those with available data for the essential variables of this study and for the period chosen as well as the researcher's ability to retrieve the annual reports and financial statements.

The purposive sampling technique was adopted in this study. This was to enable the researcher to draw an appropriate sample size for this study by considering a suitable technique of selection. In drawing the sample size, only those companies operating as single entities as well as the possibility of the researcher being able to

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retrieve the financial statements for the extraction of applicable data in line with the respective variables of this study.

The data for this study were collected from the financial statements of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria sampled for this study from the period of 2013 to 2023. The data obtained from the annual reports and financial statements of quoted manufacturing companies were the ones associated with key variables of accounting information and market value. The type of data used were panel data obtained from the year 2013 to 2023. The method used in data collection process was secondary because the study depended on historical data and the data

were available on financial statements of the sampled quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria already prepared and published by management of entities.

The dependent variable of this study was market value measured by market capitalization (MCAP) and the independent variable was accounting information decomposed into Net Asset (NA) and Cash Flow (CF). From the variable description, the justification for the adoption of panel linear regression technique in establishing the influence of independent variables on dependent variable was clearly observed. These were presented on Table 3.1:

Table 3.1: Variable Description

S/N	Variable	Abbr.	Measurement	Apriori Expectation
1.	Market Value	MV	Market value is measured as stock price per share multiplied by equity shares outstanding of a quoted company.	
2.	Net Asset	NA	Net asset is measured as total assets less current liabilities of a quoted company.	+
3.	Cash Flow	CF	Cash flow is measured as the aggregate of net cash flow from operating, investing and financing activities of a quoted company.	+
4.	Revenue (Control Variable)	REV	Revenue is the aggregate sales made in an accounting period.	+
5.	Total Equity (Control Variable)	TE	Total equity is the sum of share capital, share premium and retained earnings.	+

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2025)

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The key variables of this study as stated on the Table 3.1 regarded as variable description were broadly classified into two and these were accounting information (AIF) and market value (MV). Market Value (MV) was measured by Market Capitalization (MCAP) while accounting information (AIF) was decomposed into sub-variables such as net asset (NA) and cash flow (CF). Revenue (REV) and Total Equity (TE) were chosen as control variables of this study. The nature of data collected and the objectives of this study suggested the application of panel linear regression technique as suitable statistical tool adopted in establishing the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Based on the gap in the literature and in line with previous studies conducted in the related area of interest, the adapted empirical models were stated appropriately in line with the variables in each of the objectives of this study:

$$MCAP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NA_{ij} + e_t$$

Equation (3.1a)

$$MCAP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CF_{ij} + e_t$$

Equation (3.2a)

$$MCAP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NA_{ij} + \beta_2 CF_{ij} + e_t$$

Equation (3.3a)

The formulated models with the inclusion of the control variables were stated accordingly:

$$MCAP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NA_{ij} + \beta_2 REV_{ij} + \beta_3 TE_{ij} + e_t$$

Equation (3.1b)

$$MCAP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CF_{ij} + \beta_2 REV_{ij} + \beta_3 TE_{ij} + e_t$$

Equation (3.2b)

$$MCAP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NA_{ij} + \beta_2 CF_{ij} + \beta_3 REV_{ij} + \beta_4 TE_{ij} + e_t$$

Equation (3.3b)

The data for this study were analysed using both descriptive and inferential analytical tools. The descriptive statistics was used to examine the nature of the data relating to both accounting information and market value while the inferential statistics was used to establish the influence of variables accounting information on market value measured by market capitalization. In this regard, mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum were the tools used to describe the nature of the applicable data collected. The inferential statistics was the multiple linear regression that used in this study based on the models formulated. In line with the nature of the data collected from the sampled entities of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, panel linear regression was adopted. Analyses were done with the assistance of E-View-10. The various statistical tools of regression used were R^2 , Adjusted R^2 , t-Statistic (t-Stat), Durbin-Watson (DW) Statistic, P-value and F-ratio. All tests were conducted at 5% level of significance.

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4 Data Analysis and Discussion of Findings

4.1 Data Analysis

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Statistics	MCAP	NA	CF	REV	TE
Mean	3.31E+08	1.30E+08	6350109.	1.23E+08	1.02E+08
Median	37051345	29942352	450612.5	36250643	20991729
Maximum	5.44E+09	1.94E+09	1.66E+09	1.30E+09	1.60E+09
Minimum	195298.3	-1.43E+09	-8.20E+08	227301.0	-78035156
Std. Dev.	8.48E+08	3.11E+08	1.17E+08	1.94E+08	2.43E+08
Skewness	3.738894	2.980717	9.604877	2.891516	4.231111
Kurtosis	16.99618	19.22577	165.7983	13.66967	22.14716
Jarque-Bera	2769.914	3286.957	295595.4	1620.137	4820.454
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	8.74E+10	3.44E+10	1.68E+09	3.23E+10	2.69E+10
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.89E+20	2.54E+19	3.58E+18	9.91E+18	1.55E+19
Observations	264	264	264	264	264

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 4.1, Market Capitalization (MCAP) had mean of ₦331,000,000. This indicated that MCAP of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study in average was ₦331,000,000. The median of ₦37,051,345 showed the middle value of MCAP for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of study. The maximum indicated that the highest value of MCAP of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦5,440,000,000. The minimum indicated that the least value of MCAP

for the period of this study was ₦195,298.3. The standard deviation indicated that the fluctuations from mean value of MCAP for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦848,000,000. The standard deviation for MCAP was very high.

From Table 4.1, Net Asset (NA) had mean of ₦130,000,000. This indicated that NA of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study in average was ₦130,000,000. The median of ₦29,942,352 showed the middle value of NA for quoted

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manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of study. The maximum indicated that the highest value of NA of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦1,940,000,000. The minimum indicated that the least value of NA for the period of this study was -₦1.430,000,000. The standard deviation indicated that the fluctuations from mean value of NA for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦3,110,000,000. The standard deviation for NA was very high.

From Table 4.1, Cash Flow (CF) had mean of ₦6,350,109. This indicated that CF of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study in average was ₦6,350,109. The median of ₦450,612.5 showed the middle value of CF for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of study. The maximum indicated that the highest value of CF of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦1,940,000,000. The minimum indicated that the least value of CF for the period of this study was -₦8,200,000,000. The standard deviation indicated that the fluctuations from mean value of CF for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦170,000,000. The standard deviation for CF was very high.

From Table 4.1, Revenue (REV) had mean of ₦123,000,000. This indicated that REV of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for

the period of this study in average was ₦123,000,000. The median of ₦36,250,643 showed the middle value of REV for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of study. The maximum indicated that the highest value of REV of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦1,300,000,000. The minimum indicated that the least value of REV for the period of this study was ₦227,301. The standard deviation indicated that the fluctuations from mean value of REV for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦194,000,000. The standard deviation for REV was very high.

From Table 4.1, Total Equity (TE) had mean of ₦102,000,000. This indicated that TE of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study in average was ₦102,000,000. The median of ₦20,991,729 showed the middle value of TE for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of study. The maximum indicated that the highest value of TE of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦1,600,000,000. The minimum indicated that the least value of TE for the period of this study was -₦78,035,156. The standard deviation indicated that the fluctuations from mean value of TE for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦243,000,000. The standard deviation for TE was very high.

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4.1.2 Correlation Matrix

The association between the variables of this study were ascertained using correlation

coefficient. The computation of correlation coefficient for all the variables were presented on Table 4.2:

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix

Correlation	CF	MCAP	NA	REV	TE
CF	1.000000				
MCAP	0.479495	1.000000			
NA	0.068967	0.854963	1.000000		
REV	0.044977	0.734155	0.344442	1.000000	
TE	0.054516	0.872667	0.398830	0.370057	1.000000
Probability	CF	MCAP	NA	REV	TE
CF	-----				
MCAP	0.0034	-----			
NA	0.2642	0.0000	-----		
REV	0.4668	0.0000	0.0000	-----	
TE	0.3777	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-----

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 4.2, it was discovered that the relationship between all the independent variables with each other were less than sixty percent (60%). This showed that there was no indication of multi-collinearity in pairs of independent variables of this study. The predictors were independently used to establish the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The relationship between NA and MCAP was 85.49% (p-value<0.05), the

relationship between CF and MCAP was 47.94% (p-value<0.05), the relationship between REV and MCAP was 73.42% (p-value<0.05) and the relationship between TE and MCAP was 87.27% (p-value<0.05).

4.1.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.1.3.1 Test of Hypothesis One

The pooled panel linear regression analysis was conducted in line with Market Value (MCAP) and Net Asset (NA) as presented on Table 4.3:

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Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

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Table 4.3: Pooled Panel Linear Regression

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-20078474	28422360	-0.706432	0.4806
NA	0.920796	0.179061	5.142371	0.0000
REV	0.477513	0.197048	2.423335	0.0161
TE	1.692278	0.239796	7.057168	0.0000
R-squared	0.792175			
Adjusted R-squared	0.789777			
F-statistic	330.3517	Durbin-Watson stat		1.521411
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Dependent Variable: MCAP

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 4.3, Net Asset (NA), Revenue (REV) and Total Equity (TE) exerted positive and significant influence on market value (MCAP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This indicated that a percentage increase in NA, REV and TE brought about significant increase in MCAP of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The result of the analysis in respect to NA, REV and TE were in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researcher. The constant value of -N20,078,474 indicated the value of MCAP as NA, REV and TE were held constant and insignificant.

R² indicated that 79.22% variation in MCAP was attributed to the influence of NA, REV and TE of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria and Adjusted R² indicated that exact 78.98%

variation in MCAP was attributed to the influence of NA of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria and was significant. The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 1.5214 indicated that there was no first-order autocorrelation in the model. The null hypothesis, which states that net asset does not significantly influence market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was rejected and the alternative hypothesis, which states that net asset significantly influence market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was accepted.

4.1.3.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

The pooled panel linear regression analysis was conducted in line with Market Value (MCAP) and Cash Flow (CF) as presented on Table 4.4:

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Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

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E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

Advance Scholars Publication

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Table 4.4: Pooled Panel Linear Regression

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-22824117	28689817	-0.795548	0.4270
CF	0.958974	0.207802	4.614845	0.0000
REV	0.662766	0.195337	3.392940	0.0008
TE	2.612278	0.156119	16.73263	0.0000
R-squared	0.788373			
Adjusted R-squared	0.785931			
F-statistic	322.8582	Durbin-Watson stat		1.690170
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Dependent Variable: MCAP

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 4.4, Cash Flow (CF), Revenue (REV) and Total Equity (TE) had positive and significant influence on Market Value (MCAP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This indicated that a percentage increase in CF, REV and TE brought about increase in MCAP of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The results of the analysis in respect to CF, REV and TE were in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researcher. The constant value of ₦22,824,117 indicated the value of MCAP as CF, REV and TE were held constant and insignificant.

R² indicated that 78.84% variation in MCAP was attributed to the influence of CF, REV and TE of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria and Adjusted R² indicated that exact 78.59% variation in MCAP was attributed to the

influence of CF of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria and was significant. The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 1.69017 indicated that there was no first-order autocorrelation in the model. The null hypothesis, which states that cash flow does not significantly influence market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was rejected and the alternative hypothesis, which states that cash flow significantly influence market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was accepted.

4.1.3.3 Test of Hypothesis Three

The pooled panel linear regression analysis was conducted in line with Market Value (MCAP), Cash Flow (CF) and Cash Flow (CF) as presented on Table 4.5:

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Table 4.5: Pooled Panel Linear Regression

Dependent Variable: MCAP

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 4.5, Net Asset (NA), Cash Flow (CF), Revenue (REV) and Total Equity (TE) had positive and significant influence on Market Value (MCAP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This indicated that a percentage increase in NA, CF, REV and TE brought about increase in MCAP of quoted

hypothesis, which states that net asset and cash flow does not significantly influence market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was rejected and the alternative hypothesis, which states that net asset and cash flow significantly influence market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was accepted.

4.2 Discussion of the Findings

From Table 4.3, it was observed the Net Asset (NA) exerted positive and significant influence on Market Value (MCAP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This indicated that as NA increases, MCAP is also improved significantly. The result of the analyses for NA was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation. Net asset is often computed as the

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

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Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

Advance Scholars Publication

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difference between total assets less current liabilities of a quoted company in a given accounting period. The size of net asset is an important factor that provides confidence to both potential and existing investors of quoted companies because when net asset is large, it could be said that such company will always generate large revenue in different accounting periods. The composition of the net assets is often expected to have a greater proportion of non-current assets and a lesser proportion of current assets because of the principle of trade-off between current assets and profitability of an entity.

In other words, when current asset is large, it could be substantiated as a situation whereby larger liquid resources are tied down in the components of inventories and account receivable and as such, profitability is affected negatively because the liquid assets that should have been invested to generate more returns for the company is tied down in the components of current assets. When net asset is made up of greater proportion of non-current assets for a quoted entity, the direction between the variable and indicator of market value is expected to be positive because a greater proportion of non-current assets is expected to generate more revenue to the company as well as maximizing profitability. Thus, net asset is an essential variable of accounting information that provides adequate information to the various users including potential investors especially when the

composition of the net assets is properly accumulated. Net asset as an essential variable of accounting information is an embodiment of both non-current and current assets. In the computation of net asset, it is usually anticipated that the accumulated current assets should cover up the current liabilities in any accounting period to avoid the problems of illiquidity which might reduce the reputation of the entity.

Acquisition of non-current assets is usually expected to be in line with the purpose or in support of the principal activities of the business. This simply means that a quoted entity is expected to acquire only those non-current assets that are capable of supporting generation of revenue and not those that are just maintained in the organization. Also, in the accumulation of current assets, accounting policies should be stringent ones that will minimize account receivable and larger accumulation of inventories but with cash that will always meet up the obligations or commitments of the organization at any point in time. In the present study, the positive and significant influence of net asset on market capitalization, being a variable of market value, of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria is attributed to the fact that the components of the net asset are directly effective to the operation of the companies in terms of generating adequate revenue as well as meeting the short-term obligations when the need arises. This study was in line with the study of Tarik (2021) who

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Impact Factor: 5.53

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conducted a study on the value relevance of accounting information and its impact on stock prices: A study on listed pharmaceutical companies at Dhaka stock exchange of Bangladesh and found that net asset value per share exerted positive and significant influence on stock price of firms. The study was also consistent with Vijitha and Nimalathan (2014) who examined the value relevance of accounting information and share price: A study of listed manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka and found that accounting information exerted direct and material influence on stock price of the firms studied.

From Table 4.4, it was observed the Cash Flow (CF) exerted positive and substantial influence on Market Value (MCAP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This indicated that as CF increases, MCAP is also improved significantly. The result of the analyses for CF was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation. Cash flow is an essential variable of accounting information often considered by both existing and potential investors of quoted companies. This is because a quoted entity might be declaring a larger profit in different accounting period but without adequate cash to settle matured obligations usually in a short-term basis. A company like manufacturing entity is expected to have adequate cash at any given period of time because inputs for production are often expected to be purchased at daily basis and for a company without adequate cash, it become

a serious problem that might affect the operating cycle of the firm negatively. The compositions of cash flows are basically classified into three fundamental components such as flow from operating, investing and financing activities.

In all the three components, it is expected that the inflows are greater than the outflows in order to arrive at positive net balance that could add up to the cash balance of the next accounting period. For a quoted company with positive net cash flow in different accounting period is certain to exert positive influence on indicators of shareholders' wealth maximization like market capitalization. This is possible when in the components of cash flow from operating activities, cash expenses are less than cash income or inflows and similar result is achieved in the other components of cash flow regarded as investing and financing activities. For this reason, managers of quoted companies are always charged with greater responsibility of ensuring that irrelevant expenses and costs are cut down and only those expenses that could contribute to the generation of cash inflows or cash revenue are expected to be incurred. For instance, in cash flows from investing activities, the inflows are expected to be greater than outflows and even though there is acquisitions of assets that require large amount of cash, investment incomes realised from previous viable opportunities should be able to reduce the implication of the cost on the net cash flow balance in an accounting period.

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In the present study, the positive and significant influence of cash flows on market capitalization of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria could be attributed to the fact that the net cash flows generated from the three components in average for the quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria is positive and this could be confirmed from the descriptive statistics presented. The positive net cash flow balance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria showed that cash flow as the variable of accounting information influenced the wealth of the shareholders positively and significantly and as the cash flow continues to improve in future accounting period, stock price or equity share outstanding or both will improve as well. The study of the study was also consistent with that of Ihenyen and Asemota (2024) who investigated the effect of accounting information on stock price of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria and found a positive and significant influence of cash flow on stock price of the firms.

From Table 4.5, it was observed that the variables of accounting information (NA and CF) exerted significant influence on market value (MCAP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. When the attributes of accounting information individually influence the indicators of shareholders wealth such as stock price, market capitalization, it could be said that the variables of accounting information have really provided information to different users for

effective decision making including potential investors. For the variables of accounting information to exert positive influence on market capitalization, it therefore means that the managers of the entities are efficient in their strategies and policies implemented over the years and the outcomes are reflected on the items of transactions reported.

This study was in line with Kabir (2021) who carried out a study on the value relevance of accounting information on share price: Evidence from Nigerian listed companies and found that accounting information exerted positive and significant influence on market value of the entities studied. The study was also consistent with that of Chehade and Prochazka (2022) who investigated value relevance of accounting information in an emerging market: The case of IFRS adoption by non-financial listed firms in Saudi Arabia and found that accounting information exerted positive and significant influence on market value per share of the non-financial entities studied.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study was conducted to ascertain the influence of accounting information on market value (MCAP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The individual variables of accounting information were Net Asset (NA) and Cash Flow (CF). Revenue (REV) and Total Equity (TE) were selected by the researcher as control variables to reduce the spuriousness of the empirical results in individual models. From

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

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Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

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the analyses done by the researcher, it was concluded that accounting information had a significant influence on market value (MCAP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Individually, Net Asset (NA) and Cash Flow (CF) had positive and significant influence on Market Value (MCAP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria from 2013 to 2023.

In accordance with the empirical results arrived at, the following recommendations were suggested as follows:

i. The managers of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria should accumulate more assets by acquiring more of non-current assets to improve upon the market value of the entities.

ii. In the acquisition of more assets in quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, the managers should ensure that current assets maintained is greater than current liabilities for the purpose of accumulating adequate non-current assets.

iii. The managers of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria should ensure that sound and stringent accounting policies are adopted continuously in their operations where more cash revenue is realised other than accumulating more trade receivables for the purpose of achieving positive net cash flows that will raise the market value of the firms.

The following suggestions were made for the conduct of other studies in the related areas:

i. Accounting information and market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria

should be studied by other researchers by considering other attributes of accounting information such as revenue, finance costs, dividend payment and total equity as factors of accounting information.

ii. Accounting information and market value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria should be investigated by other researchers with the use of other proxies for market value like average stock price.

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

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Impact Factor: 5.53

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

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APPENDIX ONE (i)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2023

Company	Year	MCAP (₦'000)	NA (₦'000)	CF (₦'000)	REV (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2013	287,806,585.6	28,785,843.0	507,027.0	35,760,753.0	23,994,931.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2014	125,214,960.0	14,777,889.0	-14,064,052.0	30,518,586.0	11,542,026.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2015	32,211,164.3	16,765,371.0	3,739,534.0	27,825,194.0	12,285,297.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2016	19,326,698.6	15,572,673.0	-761,170.0	29,979,410.0	11,056,734.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2017	29,431,425.3	15,893,535.0	-2,163,975.0	33,079,446.0	11,742,791.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2018	18,782,020.0	17,442,636.0	3,394,229.0	35,973,479.0	12,676,146.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2019	19,815,031.1	18,900,545.0	339,014.0	39,326,807.0	13,566,235.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2020	16,903,818.0	18,735,990.0	6,656,465.0	35,407,323.0	13,549,523.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2021	16,528,177.6	21,663,584.0	6,645,194.0	42,372,034.0	13,636,354.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2022	21,599,323.0	22,625,283.0	9,462,679.0	55,212,617.0	13,302,628.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2023	35,685,838.0	-5,762,495.0	-8,109,162.0	80,378,955.0	6,513,678.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2013	167,594,301.0	139,327,211.0	8,804,057.0	225,629,747.0	87,463,784.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2014	147,459,128.0	138,251,978.0	27,623,521.0	245,701,366.0	89,678,463.0

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajfir/index.php/ajfir/index>

Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2015	87,912,442.0	115,414,431.0	-10,614,269.0	229,777,869.0	96,651,666.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2016	50,910,488.8	118,787,922.0	42,918,515.0	247,876,504.0	100,244,139.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2017	47,184,051.0	126,520,557.0	-20,533,697.0	375,225,284.0	108,115,699.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2018	152,944,696.2	182,530,056.0	7,726,248.0	389,397,836.0	151,446,296.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2019	73,807,092.0	175,728,481.0	8,726,036.0	370,205,529.0	138,929,273.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2020	87,133,372.5	213,642,790.0	5,238,183.0	394,884,217.0	146,316,890.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2021	118,091,347.2	255,256,211.0	12,877,002.0	535,881,585.0	159,878,794.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2022	127,317,233.7	274,996,957.0	-12,296,002.0	832,810,561.0	174,663,847.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2023	127,112,214.0	275,385,105.0	31,171,629.0	923,015,713.0	181,820,527.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2013	379,047,068.5	69,785,524.0	-401,585.0	122,463,538.0	121,060,621.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2014	284,929,068.5	88,079,524.0	2,168,703.0	109,202,120.0	132,328,273.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2015	245,173,625.3	76,146,288.0	2,722,504.0	118,495,882.0	48,341,376.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2016	155,708,819.2	69,882,822.0	-1,426,405.0	101,973,030.0	41,660,605.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2017	102,325,089.6	82,318,554.0	-817,026.0	125,919,817.0	42,943,015.0

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Guinness Nig. Plc	2018	214,109,840.5	110,407,853.0	8,327,577.0	142,975,792.0	87,588,174.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2019	104,371,702.3	111,936,153.0	-9,152,017.0	131,498,373.0	89,060,462.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2020	31,760,539.0	83,547,605.0	6,600,384.0	104,376,015.0	73,038,140.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2021	63,521,078.0	86,447,640.0	30,735,137.0	160,416,257.0	74,286,575.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2022	198,229,571.0	101,927,578.0	33,326,305.0	206,822,127.0	89,979,391.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2023	175,230,560.0	58,076,721.0	19,177,851.0	229,440,861.0	56,424,616.0

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	MCAP (N'000)	NA (N'000)	CF (N'000)	REV (N'000)	TE (N'000)
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2013	23,314,782.1	27,934,322.0	-624,079.0	45,709,382.0	18,553,083.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2014	30,689,866.3	35,771,100.0	7,336,425.0	55,084,305.0	20,605,248.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2015	23,790,594.0	36,083,224.0	-6,681,416.0	49,057,511.0	20,315,834.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2016	11,578,089.1	31,833,351.0	11,606,902.0	50,883,780.0	16,362,599.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2017	8,326,707.9	86,833,017.0	8,643,480.0	53,227,891.0	52,334,665.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2018	20,222,004.9	96,627,755.0	244,355.0	71,476,319.0	56,391,664.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2019	9,516,237.6	95,203,493.0	3,569,771.0	74,409,113.0	56,667,969.0

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Honeywell F. M. Plc	2020	7,771,594.0	88,621,373.0	1,504,709.0	80,450,397.0	57,285,793.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2021	9,357,633.6	85,454,093.0	10,899,974.0	109,594,730.0	57,968,678.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2022	27,755,693.0	82,686,354.0	2,845,326.0	136,427,507.0	56,429,751.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2023	17,446,435.6	74,826,803.0	-5,662,187.0	147,350,739.0	32,976,289.0
Int Breweries Plc	2013	68,349,919.7	15,177,427.0	724,043.0	17,388,632.0	9,380,173.0
Int Breweries Plc	2014	79,720,850.0	17,766,093.0	-649,014.0	18,493,907.0	11,269,923.0
Int Breweries Plc	2015	62,261,325.0	20,196,382.0	460,289.0	20,649,295.0	12,168,259.0
Int Breweries Plc	2016	67,499,182.5	17,541,372.0	248,390.0	23,269,364.0	13,997,391.0
Int Breweries Plc	2017	468,474,479.0	64,123,095.0	8,808,269.0	36,527,807.0	39,225,363.0
Int Breweries Plc	2018	262,173,791.0	191,399,485.0	639,831.0	120,610,825.0	35,160,923.0
Int Breweries Plc	2019	81,660,689.0	161,040,471.0	42,834,794.0	132,351,500.0	7,463,701.0
Int Breweries Plc	2020	159,829,304.6	154,724,885.0	19,001,483.0	136,790,573.0	151,733,857.0
Int Breweries Plc	2021	132,967,236.6	144,273,781.0	15,994,339.0	182,298,045.0	135,303,901.0
Int Breweries Plc	2022	126,251,719.6	273,410,419.0	30,776,962.0	218,650,266.0	117,330,433.0

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Int Breweries Plc	2023	128,937,926.4	516,392,011.0	-6,622,586.0	264,278,299.0	124,577,455.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2013	4,241,160.0	1,989,314.0	852,519.0	11,701,741.0	1,605,717.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2014	3,929,310.0	2,078,901.0	-99,135.0	11,392,017.0	1,773,912.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2015	32,315,847.9	1,931,767.0	415,773.0	10,529,075.0	1,480,063.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2016	5,167,302.7	1,752,309.0	-553,634.0	979,038.0	1,250,937.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2017	1,124,442.0	1,357,330.0	81,420.0	1,330,536.0	1,239,578.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2018	1,167,210.0	2,543,327.0	86,369.0	2,861,752.0	1,174,262.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2019	766,260.0	2,107,588.0	-133,525.0	4,149,917.0	1,150,712.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2020	766,260.0	3,708,780.0	5,960,807.0	8,841,135.0	2,768,993.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2021	1,104,840.0	3,531,497.0	-1,789,893.0	8,667,751.0	2,787,771.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2022	1,603,800.0	3,523,742.0	440,936.0	15,232,820.0	2,854,469.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2023	2,129,490.0	7,631,847.0	799,639.0	16,161,840.0	6,579,567.0

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	MCAP (₦'000)	NA (₦'000)	CF (₦'000)	REV (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)
Nascon Allied Plc	2013	39,715,075.6	7,624,451.0	-2,873,203.0	10,837,261.0	6,892,626.0

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Nascon Allied Plc	2014	16,479,504.4	7,209,770.0	-305,128.0	11,250,544.0	6,307,306.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2015	18,943,481.7	8,343,326.0	1,660,942.0	16,178,197.0	-1,324,719.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2016	22,520,223.0	9,478,314.0	-51,388.0	18,291,792.0	2,415,183.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2017	49,014,603.0	13,507,917.0	6,984,671.0	27,064,325.0	-1,854,607.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2018	47,689,884.0	14,181,709.0	-6,888,764.0	25,769,352.0	-3,974,158.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2019	34,310,222.1	19,926,528.0	1,072,758.0	27,487,788.0	11,089,285.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2020	38,416,851.0	18,787,329.0	-1,058,364.0	28,010,059.0	12,719,820.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2021	34,972,581.6	20,303,323.0	4,418,197.0	33,279,688.0	14,630,680.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2022	29,143,818.0	25,041,212.0	5,963,734.0	58,786,251.0	19,042,366.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2023	139,625,382.6	33,932,241.0	12,835,057.0	80,828,373.0	27,471,858.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2013	951,187,200.0	75,389,998.0	9,902,438.0	133,084,076.0	23,004,468.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2014	801,969,708.0	61,958,823.0	11,249,604.0	143,328,982.0	30,056,784.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2015	681,684,160.0	59,483,196.0	10,157,603.0	151,271,526.0	38,007,074.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2016	642,051,360.0	48,552,498.0	38,572,068.0	181,910,977.0	30,878,075.0

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Nestle Nig. Plc	2017	1,233,364,809.4	67,123,633.0	-39,771,803.0	244,151,411.0	44,878,177.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2018	1,177,094,160.0	70,216,941.0	2,943,591.0	266,274,621.0	50,220,486.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2019	1,165,125,054.4	67,838,884.0	-10,126,345.0	284,035,255.0	45,557,630.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2020	1,192,947,280.0	80,154,645.0	54,458,644.0	287,084,087.0	29,296,984.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2021	1,233,769,064.0	114,720,519.0	41,508,734.0	351,822,329.0	21,378,209.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2022	764,041,118.4	196,639,469.0	16,940,656.0	446,819,260.0	30,291,224.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2023	871,921,600.0	291,136,698.0	48,883,853.0	547,118,754.0	-78,035,156.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2013	1,015,822,669.9	249,381,069.0	14,643.0	268,613,518.0	112,359,185.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2014	1,000,092,241.4	234,674,537.0	4,060,149.0	266,372,475.0	171,964,263.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2015	862,686,297.6	216,051,533.0	19,577,974.0	293,905,792.0	172,233,465.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2016	938,726,385.8	222,783,115.0	25,393,918.0	313,743,147.0	165,805,542.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2017	863,025,663.8	226,027,635.0	4,110,203.0	365,798,057.0	178,150,934.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2018	546,988,096.8	248,383,173.0	-2,072,568.0	350,226,472.0	166,644,184.0

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Nig. Breweries Plc	2019	377,453,774.4	243,063,174.0	-6,963,672.0	323,002,120.0	167,564,562.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2020	358,261,209.6	235,361,447.0	23,991,008.0	337,006,267.0	161,150,877.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2021	319,876,080.0	213,216,675.0	13,583,111.0	437,195,534.0	172,139,303.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2022	327,872,982.0	581,149,386.0	5,309,326.0	550,477,627.0	180,879,079.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2023	287,888,472.0	213,328,054.0	5,328,332.0	599,508,761.0	65,168,612.0

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	MCAP (₦'000)	NA (₦'000)	CF (₦'000)	REV (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)
Nig. Enamel Plc	2013	1,703,750.4	1,519,478.0	-113,715.0	2,516,038.0	1,183,938.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2014	1,703,750.4	1,563,296.0	-854,405.0	2,569,751.0	1,241,581.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2015	1,680,307.2	1,616,681.0	-1,742,785.0	2,608,286.0	1,305,603.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2016	1,572,595.2	1,706,351.0	1,144,178.0	2,795,190.0	1,414,566.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2017	1,548,518.4	1,712,670.0	-1,482,238.0	2,528,319.0	1,427,112.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2018	1,680,307.2	1,671,074.0	2,376,540.0	1,650,999.0	1,423,779.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2019	1,680,307.2	1,432,134.0	330,924.0	740,232.0	1,182,145.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2020	1,680,307.2	1,087,713.0	500,394.0	497,933.0	831,339.0

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Nig. Enamel Plc	202 1	1,513,036.8	798,316.0	473.0	297,666.0	555,806.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	202 2	1,231,718.4	373,130.0	3,656.0	354,804.0	144,745.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	202 3	1,467,417.6	1,928,002. 0	1,413,216.0	227,301.0	1,830,802. 0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	201 3	202,414,866.5	50,899,333 .0	6,348,916.0	71,343,088.0	46,436,857 .0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	201 4	142,937,136.0	47,013,687. 0	- 4,394,178.0	72,905,679.0	42,538,582 .0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	201 5	115,858,489.7	30,342,774. 0	- 2,215,574.0	73,126,070.0	26,584,929 .0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	201 6	81,831,510.4	37,900,474. 0	2,951,255.0	69,527,537.0	33,792,289 .0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2017	72,897,939.4	38,036,404 .0	-542,099.0	54,761,729.0	34,076,230 .0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	201 8	82,784,424.6	37,416,389. 0	8,177,384.0	58,483,029. 0	33,750,379. 0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	201 9	32,160,855.6	38,038,012. 0	- 10,173,035. 0	47,200,919.0	33,816,582. 0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	202 0	21,837,618.0	30,847,908 .0	6,586,192.0	38,939,223. 0	23,896,811. 0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	202 1	21,837,618.0	29,541,929. 0	3,997,950.0	47,832,559.0	23,045,466 .0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	202 2	45,461,950.2	29,264,196. 0	23,003,552. 0	58,264,660. 0	23,872,147. 0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	202 3	106,011,709.2	28,672,468. 0	23,241,972. 0	67,423,111.0	28,677,468 .0
Unilever Nig. Plc	201 3	203,541,432.4	15,681,474. 0	3,114,282.0	60,004,119.0	9,347,922. 0

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Unilever Plc	Nig.	2014	135,442,068.4	13,879,091.0	-3,231,679.0	55,754,309.0	7,478,808.0
Unilever Plc	Nig.	2015	155,682,712.7	15,474,831.0	7,118,051.0	59,221,748.0	8,003,253.0
Unilever Plc	Nig.	2016	132,604,594.9	18,977,920.0	14,574,569.0	69,777,061.0	11,689,943.0
Unilever Plc	Nig.	2017	235,545,246.0	84,389,058.0	43,019,454.0	85,193,369.0	75,908,375.0
Unilever Plc	Nig.	2018	212,565,222.0	88,676,320.0	6,601,911.0	92,899,969.0	82,789,543.0
Unilever Plc	Nig.	2019	126,390,132.0	68,869,435.0	21,683,361.0	60,486,835.0	66,528,350.0
Unilever Plc	Nig.	2020	79,855,583.4	63,718,681.0	1,152,134.0	61,959,678.0	62,129,120.0
Unilever Plc	Nig.	2021	83,302,587.0	68,070,846.0	18,798,955.0	70,523,695.0	65,761,668.0
Unilever Plc	Nig.	2022	66,642,069.6	70,012,735.0	10,872,935.0	88,570,826.0	67,564,716.0
Unilever Plc	Nig.	2023	85,026,088.8	82,505,298.0	10,510,221.0	103,879,730.0	74,509,103.0

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	MCAP (₦'000)	NA (₦'000)	CF (₦'000)	REV (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)
Berger Paint Plc	2013	2,318,592.0	2,828,975.0	389,716.0	2,710,986.0	2,476,257.0
Berger Paint Plc	2014	2,477,995.2	2,823,614.0	-716,499.0	3,082,930.0	2,459,830.0
Berger Paint Plc	2015	2,898,240.0	2,752,167.0	178,863.0	3,022,264.0	2,587,330.0

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajfir/index.php/ajfir/index>

Berger Paint Plc	2016	1,854,873.6	2,795,918.0	-113,792.0	2,602,824.0	2,604,181.0
Berger Paint Plc	2017	2,457,707.5	3,230,892.0	268,798.0	3,012,648.0	2,641,145.0
Berger Paint Plc	2018	2,492,486.4	3,250,261.0	-176,601.0	3,377,223.0	2,813,052.0
Berger Paint Plc	2019	1,956,312.0	3,578,424.0	-193,521.0	3,584,804.0	3,073,400.0
Berger Paint Plc	2020	2,130,206.4	3,643,005.0	139,911.0	3,837,582.0	3,146,972.0
Berger Paint Plc	2021	2,477,995.2	3,671,608.0	-138,970.0	4,964,796.0	3,230,703.0
Berger Paint Plc	2022	1,738,944.0	3,838,332.0	278,209.0	6,331,634.0	3,323,445.0
Berger Paint Plc	2023	3,767,712.0	4,554,102.0	302,199.0	7,910,181.0	3,531,401.0
Beta Glass Plc	2013	6,009,663.4	17,743,168.0	1,001,650.0	14,096,123.0	13,753,157.0
Beta Glass Plc	2014	11,574,351.8	19,254,430.0	962,787.0	16,632,879.0	15,952,981.0
Beta Glass Plc	2015	22,268,752.9	21,644,062.0	830,118.0	15,953,224.0	17,578,125.0
Beta Glass Plc	2016	12,634,292.4	26,193,673.0	4,023,377.0	19,091,192.0	21,474,964.0
Beta Glass Plc	2017	21,378,802.7	29,168,660.0	-1,162,576.0	22,186,258.0	25,145,114.0
Beta Glass Plc	2018	28,458,406.2	32,356,317.0	1,690,386.0	26,321,014.0	29,627,573.0
Beta Glass Plc	2019	22,413,744.8	37,047,712.0	898,375.0	29,412,252.0	34,558,001.0
Beta Glass Plc	2020	23,083,707.2	39,151,335.0	953,441.0	25,637,010.0	37,189,718.0

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Beta Glass Plc	2021	22,058,764.6	45,712,381.0	4,346,827.0	36,982,815.0	42,127,418.0
Beta Glass Plc	2022	23,758,653.6	49,801,955.0	181,440.0	54,340,363.0	46,263,350.0
Beta Glass Plc	2023	35,637,980.4	103,313,293.0	2,197,841.0	62,905,451.0	52,005,006.0
Champion B. Plc	2013	15,219,000.0	-4,545,559.0	124,789.0	2,233,259.0	-4,608,386.0
Champion B. Plc	2014	50,256,000.0	6,013,452.0	417,152.0	3,302,383.0	5,870,431.0
Champion B. Plc	2015	26,463,696.5	7,255,162.0	633,456.0	3,501,845.0	7,121,637.0
Champion B. Plc	2016	19,182,265.2	7,753,067.0	-50,554.0	3,864,943.0	7,670,860.0
Champion B. Plc	2017	16,285,351.7	8,461,288.0	-807,917.0	4,777,313.0	8,135,460.0
Champion B. Plc	2018	15,580,697.0	8,181,519.0	-125,402.0	4,763,757.0	7,935,532.0
Champion B. Plc	2019	7,438,021.2	8,416,927.0	516,073.0	6,927,177.0	8,031,796.0
Champion B. Plc	2020	6,733,366.6	9,116,860.0	323,279.0	7,051,806.0	8,042,994.0
Champion B. Plc	2021	18,399,315.6	10,051,065.0	1,846,793.0	10,518,497.0	9,219,643.0
Champion B. Plc	2022	43,062,228.0	12,526,624.0	-683,219.0	12,288,893.0	11,119,384.0
Champion B. Plc	2023	28,421,070.5	12,564,673.0	255,810.0	12,704,274.0	11,195,299.0

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

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Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	MCAP (₦'000)	NA (₦'000)	CF (₦'000)	REV (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)
BUA Cement Plc	2013	14,765,966.5	10,956,532.0	475,142.0	15,311,004.0	8,284,619.0
BUA Cement Plc	2014	13,006,617.3	12,283,858.0	-180,694.0	15,119,051.0	9,445,658.0
BUA Cement Plc	2015	11,749,939.3	13,001,560.0	532,444.0	13,037,847.0	10,144,768.0
BUA Cement Plc	2016	5,981,787.3	14,528,241.0	1,458,806.0	14,087,553.0	11,493,272.0
BUA Cement Plc	2017	11,938,441.0	17,482,722.0	670,179.0	19,588,261.0	14,412,207.0
BUA Cement Plc	2018	254,983,938.8	336,192,212.0	-1,537,825.0	31,721,962.0	333,487,688.0
BUA Cement Plc	2019	237,897,386.2	343,305,114.0	4,042,576.0	32,148,368.0	340,771,502.0
BUA Cement Plc	2020	2,619,407,781.9	558,202,389.0	1,664,771,860.0	209,443,487.0	375,954,728.0
BUA Cement Plc	2021	2,270,604,935.7	583,152,353.0	-73,623,111.0	257,327,091.0	398,116,748.0
BUA Cement Plc	2022	3,310,240,603.5	848,255,728.0	14,330,072.0	360,989,105.0	411,112,542.0
BUA Cement Plc	2023	3,857,149,920.6	838,648,750.0	53,938,322.0	459,998,999.0	385,224,150.0
Cutix Plc	2013	1,285,766.5	674,121.0	20,326.0	1,929,477.0	597,554.0
Cutix Plc	2014	1,673,257.8	1,048,516.0	-535,134.0	2,234,959.0	699,703.0
Cutix Plc	2015	1,602,804.8	1,045,921.0	-12,837.0	2,358,412.0	743,711.0

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Cutix Plc	2016	1,224,120.2	1,135,423.0	56,978.0	2,835,862.0	870,217.0
Cutix Plc	2017	783,789.2	1,217,386.0	36,259.0	3,675,712.0	1,013,969.0
Cutix Plc	2018	2,597,952.9	1,476,749.0	-11,126.0	5,057,374.0	1,299,292.0
Cutix Plc	2019	6,516,928.4	1,828,845.0	8,256.0	5,434,107.0	1,613,091.0
Cutix Plc	2020	2,131,211.7	2,314,154.0	55,008.0	5,025,500.0	1,805,638.0
Cutix Plc	2021	3,892,543.7	2,492,941.0	-59,002.0	6,745,521.0	2,214,333.0
Cutix Plc	2022	8,595,300.2	2,977,344.0	12,002.0	7,852,391.0	2,767,160.0
Cutix Plc	2023	7,925,994.0	3,464,638.0	-7,389.0	9,225,071.0	3,232,801.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2013	3,731,700,846.9	670,706,934.0	25,744,813.0	371,551,567.0	571,562,826.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2014	3,408,101,600.0	757,611,387.0	51,093,716.0	371,534,117.0	638,543,114.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2015	2,896,800,000.0	983,889,000.0	1,612,000.0	389,215,000.0	748,479,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2016	2,961,211,200.0	1,112,338,000.0	47,548,000.0	426,129,000.0	981,367,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2017	3,919,200,000.0	1,267,131,000.0	36,958,000.0	552,364,000.0	991,017,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2018	3,232,488,000.0	1,437,215,000.0	6,512,000.0	618,301,000.0	1,293,548,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2019	2,419,680,000.0	1,413,409,000.0	53,193,000.0	610,247,000.0	1,282,249,000.0

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Dang. Cem. Plc	2020	4,173,096,000.0	1,577,447,000.0	13,061,000.0	719,945,000.0	1,352,377,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2021	4,379,280,000.0	1,744,440,000.0	134,961,000.0	993,399,000.0	1,461,472,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2022	4,447,440,000.0	1,882,623,000.0	134,881,000.0	1,205,401,000.0	1,491,535,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2023	5,435,760,000.0	1,943,232,000.0	154,024,000.0	1,297,639,000.0	1,602,964,000.0

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	MCAP (₦'000)	NA (₦'000)	CF (₦'000)	REV (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2013	140,400,000.0	60,866,092.0	-18,175,509.0	102,467,361.0	57,125,832.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2014	76,200,000.0	64,067,370.0	10,795,694.0	94,103,677.0	51,413,720.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2015	72,360,000.0	62,755,716.0	2,815,330.0	100,092,221.0	58,526,202.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2016	70,800,000.0	71,154,375.0	23,939,829.0	167,409,161.0	66,388,057.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2017	240,000,000.0	106,420,177.0	7,480,536.0	198,120,639.0	99,207,358.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2018	183,000,000.0	112,490,123.0	25,106,272.0	146,549,176.0	107,180,126.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2019	163,200,000.0	112,159,609.0	26,318,320.0	78,608,142.0	106,849,582.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2020	213,785,052.8	136,528,272.0	20,731,117.0	206,360,656.0	125,302,902.0

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Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2021	211,355,677.2	142,161,438.0	57,659,824.0	276,054,781.0	129,830,169.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2022	194,957,391.9	185,799,322.0	72,602,333.0	403,245,988.0	172,029,685.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2023	692,372,046.0	82,139,967.0	-21,367,144.0	441,452,953.0	81,809,910.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2013	345,184,000.0	120,532,421.0	11,379,623.0	97,174,505.0	92,641,665.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2014	322,297,599.7	307,101,082.0	18,562,520.0	105,848,657.0	276,664,338.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2015	400,831,376.0	333,715,546.0	2,414,850.0	114,558,245.0	302,601,869.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2016	213,255,359.9	425,005,965.0	12,398,708.0	87,198,416.0	340,094,143.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2017	243,103,833.6	333,714,172.0	15,801,940.0	177,170,362.0	264,768,895.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2018	107,984,203.5	403,821,619.0	-13,291,384.0	187,043,475.0	255,743,725.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2019	246,449,309.4	410,865,615.0	31,697,689.0	188,407,004.0	361,421,559.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2020	339,069,147.9	380,809,940.0	14,584,890.0	202,530,359.0	373,974,933.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2021	385,781,762.1	400,198,026.0	819,736,800.0	262,299,071.0	395,349,470.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2022	386,587,152.0	439,250,256.0	121,992,143.0	340,633,999.0	434,275,803.0

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Lafarge Africa Plc	2023	507,395,637.0	-1,432,879,041.0	50,512,531.0	372,513,521.0	450,120,336.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2013	458,250.0	1,846,763.0	58,654.0	1,500,112.0	622,382.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2014	295,750.0	1,744,667.0	-89,995.0	1,340,104.0	581,626.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2015	195,298.3	1,706,432.0	-98,466.0	1,187,236.0	638,100.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2016	262,341.0	1,394,337.0	-31,728.0	1,091,000.0	423,698.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2017	363,341.4	617,014.0	13,717.0	1,097,061.0	302,969.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2018	293,659.5	785,251.0	4,863.0	970,134.0	621,063.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2019	268,773.1	755,594.0	1,457,286.0	1,106,116.0	607,570.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2020	248,864.0	1,679,765.0	908,858.0	827,599.0	1,716,076.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2021	228,954.9	1,029,847.0	-993,336.0	1,118,098.0	1,003,158.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2022	1,129,842.6	1,438,895.0	-69,210.0	1,435,032.0	1,396,775.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2023	1,786,843.5	1,668,372.0	195,228.0	2,266,791.0	1,632,744.0

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	MCAP (₦'000)	NA (₦'000)	CF (₦'000)	REV (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2013	1,138,410.0	4,164,130.0	237,722.0	15,519,856.0	3,267,313.0

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Vitafoam Nig. Plc	201 4	1,220,310.0	4,367,599.0	309,589.0	15,519,856.0	3,747,004. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	201 5	4,835,376.0	4,978,063.0	-335,359.0	15,155,102.0	3,802,832. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	201 6	2,490,547.3	5,328,611.0	-421,094.0	12,189,558.0	4,375,223. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	201 7	2,177,926.3	5,352,469.0	103,160.0	15,921,022.0	4,463,206. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	201 8	3,042,844.4	7,272,369.0	1,284,706. 0	17,612,291.0	4,822,994. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	201 9	4,878,291.6	7,895,693.0	788,434.0	20,330,040. 0	5,932,044. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	202 0	7,505,064.0	12,147,442. 0	5,699,204. 0	21,521,097.0	8,687,013. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	202 1	21,389,432.4	14,458,819. 0	3,718,395. 0	32,007,979. 0	12,401,122. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	202 2	26,205,181.8	16,699,991. 0	997,578.0	42,128,595. 0	15,013,073. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	202 3	27,518,568.0	17,593,135.0	6,218,105. 0	47,723,375.0	16,178,032. 0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	201 3	69,318,838.0	70,184,216. 0	14,805,056 .0	20,233,013. 0	26,558,057 .0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	201 4	64,482,640.0	64,281,221. 0	15,526,223 .0	16,500,881. 0	17,790,009 .0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	201 5	67,706,772.0	45,042,499. 0	16,429,120 .0	16,600,804. 0	7,122,238. 0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	201 6	67,706,772.0	95,582,939. 0	15,782,798 .0	25,201,505. 0	41,214,522. 0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	201 7	67,706,772.0	87,405,770. 0	- 31,947,179. 0	35,893,598. 0	49,997,071 .0

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Notore C. Indust. Plc	2018	100,754,125.0	131,143,154.0	37,205,859.0	26,823,881.0	48,123,262.0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2019	100,754,125.0	146,639,289.0	3,222,374.0	21,418,883.0	68,940,707.0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2020	100,754,125.0	168,028,382.0	-301,329.0	18,799,043.0	62,465,762.0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2021	100,754,125.0	137,877,454.0	529,189.0	25,484,427.0	53,439,120.0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2022	100,754,125.0	191,655,764.0	1,185,182.0	32,226,698.0	76,103,166.0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2023	100,754,125.0	211,641,711.0	1,986,204.0	21,545,162.0	43,530,143.0
CAP Plc	2013	33,915,000.0	1,350,439.0	190,248.0	6,195,824.0	1,268,148.0
CAP Plc	2014	26,600,000.0	1,254,883.0	-366,718.0	6,987,604.0	1,180,573.0
CAP Plc	2015	26,320,000.0	1,575,462.0	-626,543.0	7,056,876.0	1,520,133.0
CAP Plc	2016	21,385,000.0	2,420,571.0	-402,323.0	6,813,984.0	2,283,490.0
CAP Plc	2017	24,220,000.0	2,342,269.0	488,648.0	7,113,950.0	2,242,220.0
CAP Plc	2018	24,395,000.0	2,935,992.0	-25,097.0	7,670,315.0	2,808,939.0
CAP Plc	2019	16,800,000.0	2,691,774.0	-25,102.0	8,410,650.0	2,521,684.0
CAP Plc	2020	14,000,000.0	3,744,808.0	1,451,080.0	8,876,191.0	3,744,808.0
CAP Plc	2021	15,331,657.0	4,583,471.0	3,176,378.0	14,207,818.0	4,409,788.0

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

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September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajfir/index.php/ajfir/index>

CAP Plc	202			1,189,086.	19,208,470.	6,599,601.
	2	14,502,514.4	6,936,147.0	0	0	0
CAP Plc	202			1,235,346.	23,890,279.	7,969,707.
	3	16,987,495.8	8,466,760.0	0	0	0

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Where MCAP= Market Capitalization, NA= Net Asset, CF= Cash Flow, REV= Revenue and TE= Total Equity.

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APPENDIX TWO (ii)

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2023

Company	Year	TA (N'000)	CL (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	TE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)	M P (N)	REV (N'000)
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2013	43,172,624.0	14,386,781.0	6,621,476.0	2,977,964.0	3,136,485.0	6,023,220.0	23,994,931.0	3,130,374.0	91.9	35,760,753.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2014	28,820,107.0	14,042,218.0	1,419,524.0	1,129,439.0	14,354,137.0	1,512,687.0	11,542,026.0	3,130,374.0	40.0	30,518,586.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2015	28,417,005.0	11,651,634.0	5,797,705.0	787,360.0	1,270,811.0	1,153,295.0	12,285,297.0	1,878,202.0	17.2	27,825,194.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2016	28,392,951.0	12,820,278.0	61,766.0	221,081.0	478,323.0	296,402.0	11,056,734.0	1,878,202.0	10.3	29,979,410.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2017	28,423,121.0	12,529,586.0	1,471,632.0	950,998.0	258,655.0	299,998.0	11,742,791.0	1,878,202.0	15.7	33,079,446.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2018	27,528,040.0	10,085,404.0	6,695,082.0	722,841.0	2,578,012.0	823,085.0	12,676,146.0	1,878,202.0	10.0	35,973,479.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2019	28,801,938.0	9,901,393.0	2,285,899.0	1,515,541.0	431,344.0	1,070,845.0	13,566,235.0	1,878,202.0	10.6	39,326,807.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2020	33,210,684.0	14,474,694.0	4,254,793.0	845,019.0	3,246,691.0	931,827.0	13,549,523.0	1,878,202.0	9.0	35,407,323.0

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Cadbury Nig. Plc	2021	43,680	22,020	674,014.0	-726,317.0	6,697,497.0	449,712.0	13,630	1,878,202.0	8.8	42,370	2,034.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2022	59,713,684.0	37,088,401.0	-2,534,928.0	-694,897.0	12,692,504.0	583,111.0	13,300	1,878,202.0	11.5	55,212,617.0	
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2023	63,430	69,190	2,797,230.0	-1,433,138.0	9,473,254.0	9,704.0	6,513,678.0	1,878,202.0	19.0	80,370	8,955.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2013	223,889,726.0	84,562,515.0	-527,216.0	-9,693,976.0	19,025,249.0	8,900,989.0	87,463,784.0	2,385,684.0	70.3	225,629,747.0	
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2014	220,145,554.0	81,893,576.0	9,934,541.0	-3,308,781.0	34,249,281.0	10,465,518.0	89,678,463.0	2,385,684.0	61.8	245,701,366.0	
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2015	231,529,878.0	116,115,447.0	10,096,781.0	-5,720,460.0	14,990,590.0	2,419,544.0	96,651,666.0	2,624,252.0	33.5	229,777,869.0	
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2016	233,296,607.0	114,508,685.0	20,924,187.0	23,900,756.0	-1,906,428.0	10,425,786.0	100,244,139.0	2,624,252.0	19.4	247,876,504.0	
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2017	343,933,157.0	217,412,600.0	-14,328,877.0	-27,311,825.0	21,107,005.0	9,829,046.0	108,115,699.0	2,624,252.0	18.0	375,225,284.0	
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2018	322,604,582.0	140,074,526.0	-24,037,585.0	-54,158,200.0	22,394,367.0	9,244,729.0	151,446,296.0	4,100,394.0	37.3	389,397,836.0	
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2019	314,058,187.0	138,329,706.0	3,544,753.0	34,258,841.0	29,077,558.0	19,317,654.0	138,929,273.0	4,100,394.0	18.0	370,205,529.0	

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Flour Mills Nig. Plc	20	314,20	100,60		-							
	0	314,2	100,6		24,98	-	12,58	146,3	4,10			394,8
	2	67,06	24,27	72,239,	9,243.	42,011,	2,571.	16,89	0,39	21.		84,217
	0	0.0	0.0	224.0	0	798.0	0	0.0	4.0	3		.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	20	380,30	125,00		-							
	0	380,3	125,0		-		20,17	159,8	4,10			535,8
	21	22,52	66,31	10,478,	9,176,	11,575,	2,489.	78,79	0,39	28.		81,58
	21	5.0	4.0	062.0	062.0	002.0	0	4.0	4.0	8		5.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	20	487,60	212,60		-							
	2	487,6	212,6		-			174,6	4,10			832,8
	2	17,576	20,61	51,219.	1,448,	13,795,	21,819	63,84	0,39	31.		10,561
	2	.0	9.0	0	389.0	610.0	,816.0	7.0	4.0	1		.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	20	719,20	443,90		-							
	2	719,2	443,9		-		60,03	14,173	4,10			923,0
	2	85,32	00,21	14,728,	14,137,	8,437.	,904.	20,52	0,39	31.		15,713
	3	2.0	7.0	972.0	836.0	0	0	7.0	4.0	0		.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	20	121,060	51,275	24,298	14,081	10,617,	5,145,	121,0	1,505			122,4
	0	0,621.	,097.0	,136.0	,901.0	820.0	149.0	60,62	,888.	251		63,53
	13	0						1.0	0	.7		8.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	20	132,30	44,240		-							
	0	132,3	44,24		-			132,3	1,505			109,2
	14	28,27	8,749.	19,157,	13,683	3,304,	2,108,	28,27	,888.	189		02,12
	14	3.0	0	202.0	,695.0	804.0	080.0	3.0	0	.2		0.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	20	122,20	46,100		-							
	0	122,2	46,10		-			48,34	1,505			118,49
	15	46,63	0,344.	32,538	8,454,	21,361,	7,794,	1,376.	,888.	162		5,882.
	15	2.0	0	,985.0	576.0	905.0	899.0	0	0	.8		0
Guinness Nig. Plc	20	136,90	67,100		-							
	0	136,9	67,10		-			41,66	1,505			101,97
	16	92,44	9,622.	1,320,	8,532,	8,425,	2,015,	0,605	,888.	103		3,030.
	16	4.0	0	097.0	239.0	931.0	886.0	.0	0	.4		0
Guinness Nig. Plc	20	146,00	63,710		-							
	0	146,0	63,71		-			42,94	1,505			125,91
	17	38,21	9,662.	18,045,	7,568,	11,294,	1,923,	3,015.	,888.	68.		9,817.
	17	6.0	0	541.0	324.0	243.0	720.0	0	0	0		0
Guinness Nig. Plc	20	153,250	42,840		-							
	0	153,25	42,84		-			87,58	2,190			142,97
	18	4,968.	7,115.	10,589,	15,629	13,366,	6,717,	8,174.	,382.	97.		5,792.
	18	0	0	789.0	,117.0	905.0	605.0	0	0	8		0

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Guinness Nig. Plc	2019	160,792,627.0	48,856,474.0	13,406,042.0	-15,827,676.0	-6,730,383.0	5,483,732.0	89,060,462.0	2,190,382.0	47.7	131,498,373.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2020	144,145,581.0	60,597,976.0	15,296,313.0	-10,415,135.0	1,719,206.0	-12,578,818.0	73,038,140.0	2,190,382.0	14.5	104,376,015.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2021	169,406,525.0	82,958,885.0	52,380,639.0	-11,376,970.0	-10,268,532.0	1,255,338.0	74,286,575.0	2,190,382.0	29.0	160,416,257.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2022	215,660,208.0	113,732,630.0	28,118,793.0	-6,844,120.0	12,051,632.0	15,651,362.0	89,979,391.0	2,190,382.0	90.5	206,822,127.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2023	241,748,144.0	183,671,423.0	34,379,964.0	-6,317,423.0	-8,884,690.0	18,168,041.0	56,424,616.0	2,190,382.0	80.0	229,440,861.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2023

Company	Year	TA (N'000)	CL (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	TE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)	M P (N)	REV (N'000)
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2013	55,437,478.0	27,503,156.0	-1,794,859.0	-6,603,263.0	7,774,043.0	2,843,520.0	18,553,083.0	7,930,198.0	2.9	45,709,382.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2014	63,830,439.0	28,059,339.0	6,431,524.0	2,261,332.0	3,166,233.0	3,351,564.0	20,605,248.0	7,930,198.0	3.9	55,084,305.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2015	67,943,444.0	31,860,220.0	5,602,147.0	-14,749,582.0	2,466,019.0	1,120,267.0	20,315,834.0	7,930,198.0	3.0	49,057,511.0

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Honeywell F. M. Plc	2016	76,046,576.0	44,213,225.0	10,131,641.0	-6,046,484.0	7,521,745.0	3,023,852.0	16,362,599.0	7,930,198.0	1.5	50,883,780.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2017	113,151,715.0	26,318,698.0	2,533,081.0	-15,856,863.0	9,746,464.0	4,304,955.0	52,334,665.0	7,930,198.0	1.1	53,227,891.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2018	124,835,013.0	28,207,258.0	14,725,910.0	-5,975,524.0	8,506,031.0	4,426,978.0	56,391,664.0	7,930,198.0	2.6	71,476,319.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2019	137,505,112.0	42,301,619.0	9,413,187.0	-5,649,275.0	194,141.0	68,368.0	56,667,969.0	7,930,198.0	1.2	74,409,113.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2020	142,261,292.0	53,639,919.0	5,417,298.0	-2,595,247.0	1,317,342.0	650,492.0	57,285,793.0	7,930,198.0	1.0	80,450,397.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2021	147,394,656.0	61,940,563.0	12,880,439.0	-741,759.0	1,238,706.0	1,125,864.0	57,968,678.0	7,930,198.0	1.2	109,594,730.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2022	149,869,159.0	67,182,805.0	553,009.0	-1,300,350.0	4,698,685.0	983,812.0	56,429,751.0	7,930,198.0	3.5	136,427,507.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2023	164,999,977.0	90,173,174.0	4,115,393.0	-6,915,289.0	5,368,495.0	256,113.0	32,976,289.0	7,930,198.0	2.2	147,350,739.0
Int Breweries Plc	2013	23,036,762.0	7,859,335.0	4,043,424.0	-6,718,935.0	11,486,402.0	2,327,342.0	9,380,173.0	3,262,526.0	21.0	17,388,632.0

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Int Breweri es Plc	2 0 14	24,37 0,540 .0	6,604 ,447.0	6,258, 083.0	- 4,097, 426.0	- 2,809, 671.0	2,105, 500.0	11,26 9,923 .0	3,294 ,250. 0	24. 2	18,49 3,907. 0
Int Breweri es Plc	2 0 15	30,171 ,590. 0	9,975, 208.0	3,151,2 32.0	- 5,754, 930.0	- 3,063, 987.0	2,395, 178.0	12,16 8,259 .0	3,294 ,250. 0	18. 9	20,64 9,295. 0
Int Breweri es Plc	2 0 16	33,48 2,106. 0	15,94 0,734. 0	7,901,7 18.0	- 3,946, 605.0	- 3,706, 723.0	2,979, 874.0	13,99 7,391. 0	3,294 ,250. 0	20. 5	23,26 9,364. 0
Int Breweri es Plc	2 0 17	232,1 49,25 1.0	168,0 26,15 6.0	44,789 ,617.0	- 42,58 0,971. 0	- 11,016, 915.0	1,395, 225.0	39,22 5,363 .0	8,595 ,862. 0	54. 5	36,52 7,807. 0
Int Breweri es Plc	2 0 18	310,2 78,92 0.0	118,87 9,435. 0	- 30,936 ,156.0	70,20 2,176. 0	101,77 8,163. 0	3,866, 298.0	35,16 0,923 .0	8,595 ,862. 0	30. 5	120,61 0,825. 0
Int Breweri es Plc	2 0 19	365,1 46,53 3.0	204,1 06,06 2.0	41,686 ,120.0	- 58,647 ,254.0	- 59,795 ,928.0	- 27,79 0,666 .0	8,595 ,862. 0	7,463, 701.0	9.5	132,35 1,500. 0
Int Breweri es Plc	2 0 20	372,6 46,40 6.0	217,9 21,521 .0	52,227, 989.0	- 29,959 ,433.0	- 3,267, 073.0	- 12,36 5,082. 0	151,73 3,857. 0	26,86 2,068 .0	6.0	136,79 0,573. 0
Int Breweri es Plc	2 0 21	469,9 53,21 5.0	325,6 79,43 4.0	52,041, 595.0	- 86,49 6,101. 0	- 50,448 ,845.0	- 17,65 6,510. 0	135,3 03,90 1.0	26,86 2,068 .0	5.0	182,2 98,04 5.0
Int Breweri es Plc	2 0 22	484,2 51,74 0.0	210,8 41,321 .0	42,666 ,952.0	- 66,524 ,156.0	- 6,919,7 58.0	- 21,62 6,290 .0	117,3 30,43 3.0	26,86 2,068 .0	4.7	218,6 50,26 6.0

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Int	2				-		-					
Breweri	0	733,11	216,7		50,08	-	59,46	124,5	26,86			264,2
es Plc	2	3,172.	21,161	74,845	8,565.	31,379,	7,375.	77,45	2,068			78,29
	3	0	.0	,867.0	0	888.0	0	5.0	.0	4.8		9.0
N Nig.	2				-		-					
Flour	0	3,623,	1,634,	1,125,7	246,18	27,030	225,1	1,605,	178,2	23.		11,701
Plc	13	417.0	103.0	31.0	2.0	.0	45.0	717.0	00.0	8		,741.0
N Nig.	2				-		-					
Flour	0	3,266,	1,187,	55,295	41,487	85,327	233,5	1,773,	178,2	22.		11,392
Plc	14	615.0	714.0	.0	.0	.0	45.0	912.0	00.0	1		,017.0
N Nig.	2				-		-					
Flour	0	2,225,	293,6	555,09	68,04	71,280	199,5	,063.	,306.	17.		9,075.
Plc	15	405.0	38.0	9.0	6.0	.0	58.0	0	0	2		0
N Nig.	2				-		-					
Flour	0	1,843,	90,90	527,39	27,218	53,460	197,2	1,250,	777,0			979,0
Plc	16	217.0	8.0	2.0	.0	.0	40.0	937.0	38.0	6.7		38.0
N Nig.	2				-		-					
Flour	0	4,337,	2,980	871,53	1,438,	2,391,	18,04	1,239,	178,2			1,330,
Plc	17	444.0	,114.0	0.0	714.0	664.0	2.0	578.0	00.0	6.3		536.0
N Nig.	2				-		-					
Flour	0	5,917,	3,374,	268,41	268,81	623,60	60,98	1,174,	178,2			2,861,
Plc	18	639.0	312.0	7.0	9.0	5.0	8.0	262.0	00.0	6.6		752.0
N Nig.	2				-		-					
Flour	0	4,992,	2,885,	1,220,5	105,36	1,248,	31,69	1,150,	178,2			4,149,
Plc	19	912.0	324.0	40.0	1.0	704.0	6.0	712.0	00.0	4.3		917.0
N Nig.	2				-		-					
Flour	0	8,491,	4,783,	31,939,	12,175,	38,154	64,63	2,768	178,2			8,841,
Plc	20	986.0	206.0	819.0	448.0	,460.0	5.0	,993.	00.0	4.3		135.0
N Nig.	2				-		-					
Flour	0	7,365,	3,833,	298,92	31,233	1,459,7	69,91	2,787,	178,2			8,667,
Plc	21	270.0	773.0	1.0	.0	39.0	9.0	771.0	00.0	6.2		751.0

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

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<https://aspjournals.org/ajfir/index.php/ajfir/index>

Nig.	2											
Flour	0				-	-		2,854				15,232
Plc	2	13,315	9,791,	2,271,8	514,61	1,316,3	80,66	,469.	178,2			,820.
	2	,128.0	386.0	79.0	0.0	33.0	8.0	0	00.0	9.0		0
Nig.	2											
Flour	0	17,82	10,195		-	-						16,161
Plc	2	7,833.	,986.	1,226,6	179,94	247,07	272,8	6,579,	178,2	12.		,840.
	3	0	0	60.0	5.0	6.0	20.0	567.0	00.0	0		0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	TA (N'000)	CL (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	TE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)	M P (N)	REV (N'000)
Nascon Allied Plc	2013	11,431,167.0	3,806,716.0	1,881,899.0	2,362,290.0	2,392,812.0	2,699,542.0	6,892,626.0	2,649,438.0	15.0	10,837,261.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2014	12,555,885.0	5,346,115.0	4,194,319.0	2,114,952.0	2,384,495.0	1,867,038.0	6,307,306.0	2,649,438.0	6.2	11,250,544.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2015	16,294,826.0	7,951,500.0	4,007,770.0	1,002,044.0	1,344,784.0	2,105,646.0	1,324,719.0	2,649,438.0	7.2	16,178,197.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2016	24,603,267.0	15,124,953.0	2,238,497.0	475,023.0	1,814,862.0	2,415,183.0	2,415,183.0	2,649,438.0	8.5	18,291,792.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2017	30,123,247.0	16,615,330.0	13,835,753.0	4,924,362.0	1,926,720.0	2,565,896.0	1,854,607.0	2,649,438.0	18.5	27,064,325.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2018	30,270,429.0	16,088,720.0	1,021,757.0	3,936,363.0	3,974,158.0	2,029,168.0	3,974,158.0	2,649,438.0	18.0	25,769,352.0

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Nascon Allied Plc	2019	38,668,792.0	18,742,264.0	6,090,389.0	-5,445,382.0	427,751.0	1,845,243.0	11,089,285.0	2,649,438.0	13.0	27,487,788.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2020	44,308,991.0	25,521,662.0	8,020,924.0	-3,984,916.0	5,094,372.0	2,690,310.0	12,719,820.0	2,649,438.0	14.5	28,010,059.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2021	40,521,398.0	20,218,075.0	4,995,649.0	1,098,432.0	1,675,884.0	2,970,982.0	14,630,680.0	2,649,438.0	13.2	33,279,688.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2022	55,530,771.0	30,489,559.0	3,499,588.0	-895,974.0	3,360,120.0	5,496,248.0	19,042,366.0	2,649,438.0	11.0	58,786,251.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2023	83,591,991.0	49,659,750.0	20,049,817.0	-893,510.0	6,321,250.0	13,728,369.0	27,471,858.0	2,649,438.0	52.7	80,828,373.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2013	108,207,480.0	32,817,482.0	35,216,402.0	-7,030,198.0	18,283,766.0	8,279.0	23,004,468.0	792,656.0	1.200	133,084,076.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2014	106,062,067.0	44,103,244.0	23,495,038.0	-7,263,538.0	27,481,104.0	5,640.0	30,056,784.0	792,656.0	1.18	143,328,982.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2015	119,215,053.0	59,731,857.0	39,877,436.0	-7,228,711.0	22,491,122.0	6,777.0	38,007,074.0	792,656.0	86.00	151,271,526.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2016	169,585,932.0	121,033,434.0	61,484,847.0	-2,842,594.0	20,070,185.0	7,924,968.0	30,878,075.0	792,656.0	81.00	181,910,977.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2017	146,804,128.0	79,680,495.0	19,235,881.0	-2,433,312.0	56,574,372.0	33,723,730.0	44,878,177.0	792,656.0	1.50	244,151,411.0

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Nestle Nig. Plc	2018	162,334,442.0	92,117,501.0	74,618,791.0	-10,984,275.0	-60,690,925.0	43,008,026.0	50,220,486.0	792,656.0	1,485.0	266,274,621.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2019	193,374,314.0	125,535,430.0	49,945,530.0	-12,328,813.0	-47,743,062.0	45,683,113.0	45,557,630.0	792,656.0	1,469.0	284,035,255.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2020	246,184,996.0	166,030,351.0	97,196,104.0	-15,718,617.0	-27,018,843.0	39,212,025.0	29,296,984.0	792,656.0	1,505.0	287,084,087.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2021	310,238,504.0	195,517,985.0	65,927,085.0	-19,969,328.0	-4,449,023.0	40,037,277.0	21,378,209.0	792,656.0	1,556.0	351,822,329.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2022	415,044,031.0	218,404,562.0	-4,432,963.0	-22,868,150.0	44,241,769.0	48,965,488.0	30,291,224.0	792,656.0	963.9	446,819,260.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2023	581,774,407.0	290,637,709.0	82,702,831.0	-55,112,317.0	21,293,339.0	-79,473,781.0	-78,035,156.0	792,656.0	1,100.0	547,118,754.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2013	349,676,784.0	100,295,715.0	95,167,850.0	-32,514,198.0	-62,639,009.0	43,080,349.0	112,359,185.0	7,562,706.0	134.3	268,613,518.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2014	349,229,163.0	114,554,626.0	60,860,045.0	-28,591,797.0	-36,328,397.0	42,520,253.0	171,964,263.0	7,562,706.0	132.2	266,372,475.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2015	356,707,123.0	140,655,590.0	72,673,843.0	-32,360,293.0	-59,891,524.0	38,049,518.0	172,233,465.0	7,929,102.0	108.8	293,905,792.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2016	367,639,915.0	144,856,800.0	70,210,871.0	-18,808,968.0	-26,007,985.0	28,396,777.0	165,805,542.0	7,929,102.0	118.4	313,743,147.0

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Nig. Breweries Plc	2017	382,726,540.0	156,698,905.0	72,113,517.0	-32,065,023.0	-35,938,291.0	33,009,292.0	178,150,934.0	7,996,902.0	107.9	365,798,057.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2018	388,766,316.0	140,383,143.0	30,567,698.0	-29,764,965.0	-2,875,301.0	19,401,169.0	166,644,184.0	7,996,902.0	68.4	350,226,472.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2019	382,503,815.0	139,440,641.0	38,576,653.0	-29,784,299.0	-15,756,026.0	16,104,763.0	167,564,562.0	7,996,902.0	47.2	323,002,120.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2020	444,437,374.0	209,075,927.0	82,724,967.0	-36,582,832.0	-22,151,127.0	7,525,621.0	161,150,877.0	7,996,902.0	44.8	337,006,267.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2021	482,639,565.0	269,422,890.0	90,847,120.0	-60,145,703.0	-44,284,528.0	12,927,163.0	172,139,303.0	7,996,902.0	40.0	437,195,534.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2022	621,318,254.0	40,168,868.0	22,506,395.0	-99,208,603.0	-82,011,534.0	13,925,086.0	180,879,079.0	7,996,902.0	41.0	550,477,627.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2023	797,362,993.0	584,034,939.0	22,528,229.0	-99,258,665.0	-82,058,768.0	105,769,222.0	65,168,612.0	7,996,902.0	36.0	599,508,761.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	TA (N'000)	CL (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	TE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)	MP (N)	REV (N'000)
Nig. Enamel Plc	2013	2,203,388.0	683,910.0	32,250.0	80,947.0	162,412.0	73,970.0	1,183,938.0	63,360.0	26.9	2,516,038.0

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Nig. Enamel Plc	2014	3,084,021.0	1,520,725.0	-719,515.0	26,592.0	-161,482.0	86,155.0	1,241,581.0	63,360.0	26.9	2,569,751.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2015	5,022,544.0	3,405,863.0	-1,652,580.0	62,000.0	-152,205.0	74,357.0	1,305,603.0	63,360.0	26.5	2,608,286.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2016	4,539,683.0	2,833,332.0	-1,255,425.0	115,424.0	-226,671.0	133,475.0	1,414,566.0	63,360.0	24.8	2,795,190.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2017	5,826,562.0	4,113,892.0	-1,054,611.0	164,956.0	-592,583.0	45,058.0	1,427,112.0	63,360.0	24.4	2,528,319.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2018	4,576,107.0	2,905,033.0	-2,697,822.0	81,492.0	-402,774.0	-3,333.0	1,423,779.0	76,032.0	22.1	1,650,999.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2019	4,381,630.0	2,949,496.0	-520,520.0	0.0	-189,596.0	241,634.0	1,182,145.0	76,032.0	22.1	740,232.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2020	4,987,799.0	3,900,086.0	-743,607.0	68,941.0	-174,272.0	350,806.0	831,339.0	76,032.0	22.1	497,933.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2021	4,619,354.0	3,821,038.0	-36,918.0	0.0	-36,445.0	275,533.0	555,806.0	76,032.0	19.9	297,666.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2022	4,408,807.0	4,035,677.0	-16,507.0	0.0	-20,163.0	431,224.0	144,745.0	76,032.0	16.2	354,804.0
Nig. Enamel Plc	2023	6,037,147.0	4,109,145.0	-1,645,184.0	3,058,400.0	0.0	1,686,057.0	1,830,802.0	76,032.0	19.3	227,301.0

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PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2 01 3	72,29 6,420. 0	21,39 7,087. 0	9,738,7 17.0	- 1,400, 485.0	- 1,989,3 16.0	5,321, 187.0	46,43 6,857 .0	3,970 ,476. 0	51. 0	71,343 ,088.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2 01 4	70,96 5,735. 0	23,95 2,048 .0	7,451,1 10.0	- 2,699, 576.0	- 9,145,7 12.0	5,082, 747.0	42,53 8,582 .0	3,970 ,476. 0	36. 0	72,90 5,679. 0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2 01 5	48,10 6,661. 0	17,76 3,887 .0	3,705,3 98.0	- 1,978, 982.0	- 3,941,9 90.0	2,168, 867.0	26,58 4,929 .0	3,970 ,476. 0	29. 2	73,126 ,070.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2 01 6	56,261 ,100.0	18,36 0,626 .0	9,331,3 47.0	- 3,104, 797.0	- 3,275,2 95.0	389,9 99.0	33,79 2,289 .0	3,970 ,476. 0	20. 6	69,527 ,537.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2 01 7	73,03 9,610. 0	35,00 3,206 .0	6,576,0 14.0	- 4,716, 888.0	- 2,401,2 25.0	2,235, 631.0	34,07 6,230 .0	3,970 ,476. 0	18. 4	54,761 ,729.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2 01 8	74,57 6,119. 0	37,15 9,730. 0	13,245, 662.0	- 2,171,0 14.0	- 2,897, 264.0	1,630, 557.0	33,75 0,379 .0	3,970 ,476. 0	20. 9	58,48 3,029. 0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2 01 9	26,27 64,315 ,676.0	26,27 7,664. 0	- 8,469, 686.0	- 931,90 9.0	- 771,44 0.0	578,3 55.0	33,81 6,582 .0	3,970 ,476. 0	8.1	47,20 0,919. 0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2 0 0	59,48 6,850. 0	28,63 8,942 .0	7,365,7 61.0	- 489,24 4.0	- 1,268,8 13.0	5,966, 995.0	23,89 6,811. 0	3,970 ,476. 0	5.5	38,93 9,223. 0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2 0 21	69,36 8,707. 0	39,82 6,778. 0	11,456, 860.0	- 6,920, 410.0	- 538,50 0.0	817,32 2.0	23,04 5,466 .0	3,970 ,476. 0	5.5	47,83 2,559. 0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2 0 2	79,87 5,535. 0	50,61 1,339. 0	3,685, 863.0	- 20,423 ,975.0	- 1,106,2 86.0	1,779, 704.0	23,87 2,147. 0	3,970 ,476. 0	11.5	58,26 4,660. 0

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PZ	2											
Cusson	0	110,82	82,15					28,67	3,970			
Nig. Plc	2	6,000	3,532.	3,865,6	3,482,	15,893,	8,528,	7,468	,476.	26.	67,42	
	3	.0	0	78.0	684.0	610.0	436.0	.0	0	7	3,111.0	
Unilever	2	43,75	28,07		-	-		9,347	3,783		60,00	
Nig. Plc	01	4,114.	2,640	11,680,	5,858,	2,707,9	4,724,	,922.	,298.	53.	4,119.	
	3	0	.0	745.0	527.0	36.0	429.0	0	0	8	0	
Unilever	2	45,73	31,85	-	-			7,478	3,783			
Nig. Plc	01	6,255.	7,164.	1,824,7	3,834,	2,427,2	2,412,	,808.	,298.	35.	55,754	
	4	0	0	95.0	183.0	99.0	343.0	0	0	8	,309.0	
Unilever	2		34,69		-	-		8,003	3,783			
Nig. Plc	01	50,172	7,653.	15,589,	4,684,	3,787,3	1,192,	,253.	,298.	41.	59,221	
	5	,484.0	0	947.0	542.0	54.0	366.0	0	0	2	,748.0	
Unilever	2		53,51		-			11,68	3,783			
Nig. Plc	01	72,491	3,389	5,990,5	3,883,	12,467,	3,071,	9,943	,298.	35.	69,777	
	6	,309.0	.0	06.0	493.0	556.0	885.0	.0	0	1	,061.0	
Unilever	2	121,08	36,69		-			75,90	5,745			
Nig. Plc	01	4,365.	5,307.	6,037,7	3,353,1	40,334	7,450,	8,375	,006.	41.	85,193	
	7	0	0	91.0	53.0	,816.0	085.0	.0	0	0	,369.0	
Unilever	2	131,84	43,16		-			82,78	5,745		92,89	
Nig. Plc	01	3,373.	7,053.	6,943,1	3,093,	3,434,7	10,552	9,543	,006.	37.	9,969.	
	8	0	0	70.0	503.0	62.0	,140.0	.0	0	0	0	
Unilever	2	103,6	34,80		-	-		66,52	5,745		60,48	
Nig. Plc	01	77,519	8,084	11,524,	4,333,	5,825,1	7,419,	8,350	,006.	22.	6,835.	
	9	.0	.0	317.0	894.0	50.0	674.0	.0	0	0	0	
Unilever	2		27,79		-	-		62,12	5,745			
Nig. Plc	2	91,517	8,857.	2,401,0	819,98	428,89	3,965,	9,120	,006.	13.	61,959	
	0	,538.0	0	16.0	4.0	8.0	921.0	.0	0	9	,678.0	
Unilever	2	108,2	40,21		-	-		65,76	5,745		70,52	
Nig. Plc	0	88,53	7,689.	20,089	927,92	363,07	3,409,	1,668	,006.	14.	3,695.	
	21	5.0	0	,953.0	0.0	8.0	174.0	.0	0	5	0	

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Advance Journal of Financial Innovation and Reporting

Adv. J. Fin. Inn. & Rept

Volume: 9; Issue: 09

September-2025

ISSN 2571-1287

E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajfir/index.php/ajfir/index>

Unilever Nig. Plc	20	125.3	55.37			-		67,56	5,745		88,57
	22	89,89	7,157.	12,031,	669,42	1,827,8	4,467,	4,716.	,006.	11.	0,826.
	22	2.0	0	343.0	9.0	37.0	084.0	0	0	6	0
Unilever Nig. Plc	20	116,30	33,79	-		-		74,50	5,745		103,87
	22	2,344.	7,046	3,784,5	1,542,1	8,267,	8,439,	9,103	,006.	14.	9,730.
	33	0	.0	29.0	76.0	868.0	895.0	.0	0	8	0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	TA (N'000)	CL (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFF (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	TE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)	MP (N)	REV (N'000)
Berger Paint Plc	2013	3,627,598.0	798,623.0	165,600.0	42,717.0	512,599.0	257,580.0	2,476,257.0	289,824.0	8.0	2,710,986.0
Berger Paint Plc	2014	3,640,145.0	816,531.0	462,336.0	30,573.0	223,590.0	148,808.0	2,459,830.0	289,824.0	8.6	3,082,930.0
Berger Paint Plc	2015	3,895,870.0	1,143,703.0	514,780.0	163,177.0	172,740.0	330,316.0	2,587,330.0	289,824.0	10.0	3,022,264.0
Berger Paint Plc	2016	4,102,265.0	1,306,347.0	758,941.0	710,249.0	162,484.0	224,007.0	2,604,181.0	289,824.0	6.4	2,602,824.0
Berger Paint Plc	2017	4,311,424.0	1,080,532.0	316,725.0	191,106.0	143,179.0	246,276.0	2,641,145.0	289,824.0	8.5	3,012,648.0
Berger Paint Plc	2018	4,535,299.0	1,285,038.0	440,335.0	342,333.0	274,603.0	320,509.0	2,813,052.0	289,824.0	8.6	3,377,223.0

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Berger Paint Plc	2019	5,066,449.0	1,488,025.0	396,290.0	-318,000.0	-271,811.0	448,733.0	3,073,400.0	289,824.0	6.8	3,584,804.0
Berger Paint Plc	2020	4,971,872.0	1,328,867.0	454,612.0	-163,667.0	-151,034.0	146,028.0	3,146,972.0	289,824.0	7.4	3,837,582.0
Berger Paint Plc	2021	5,110,669.0	1,439,061.0	265,919.0	-104,157.0	-300,732.0	135,635.0	3,230,703.0	289,824.0	8.6	4,964,796.0
Berger Paint Plc	2022	5,528,528.0	1,690,196.0	571,518.0	-71,430.0	-221,879.0	208,670.0	3,323,445.0	289,824.0	6.0	6,331,634.0
Berger Paint Plc	2023	6,610,970.0	2,056,868.0	408,196.0	-141,191.0	-35,194.0	468,797.0	3,531,401.0	289,824.0	13.0	7,910,181.0
Beta Glass Plc	2013	27,166,481.0	9,423,313.0	2,922,972.0	-1,332,973.0	-588,349.0	1,473,574.0	3,157.0	499,972.0	12.0	14,096,123.0
Beta Glass Plc	2014	26,928,387.0	7,673,957.0	4,341,369.0	-1,453,049.0	-1,925,533.0	2,390,223.0	2,981.0	499,972.0	23.2	16,632,879.0
Beta Glass Plc	2015	27,171,069.0	5,527,007.0	4,842,441.0	-3,668,180.0	-344,143.0	1,991,127.0	8,125.0	499,972.0	44.5	15,953,224.0
Beta Glass Plc	2016	33,184,130.0	6,990,457.0	4,912,545.0	-667,297.0	-221,871.0	3,799,393.0	4,964.0	499,972.0	25.3	19,091,192.0
Beta Glass Plc	2017	38,211,613.0	9,042,953.0	1,076,544.0	-2,216,587.0	-22,533.0	4,115,142.0	5,114.0	499,972.0	42.8	22,186,258.0

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Beta Glass Plc	2018	46,079,629.0	13,723,312.0	8,614,946.0	-6,487,730.0	-436,830.0	5,052,805.0	29,627,573.0	499,972.0	56.9	26,321,014.0
Beta Glass Plc	2019	52,080,362.0	15,032,650.0	5,405,503.0	-5,465,631.0	958,503.0	5,580,220.0	34,558,001.0	499,972.0	44.8	29,412,252.0
Beta Glass Plc	2020	53,963,634.0	14,812,299.0	3,361,039.0	-2,554,948.0	147,350.0	3,466,670.0	37,189,718.0	499,972.0	46.2	25,637,010.0
Beta Glass Plc	2021	63,112,410.0	17,400,029.0	7,405,003.0	-3,017,141.0	41,035.0	5,457,671.0	42,127,418.0	499,972.0	44.1	36,982,815.0
Beta Glass Plc	2022	75,944,552.0	26,142,597.0	1,312,596.0	-4,740,355.0	3,609,199.0	4,685,414.0	46,263,350.0	599,966.0	39.6	54,340,363.0
Beta Glass Plc	2023	106,851,898.0	3,538,605.0	11,385,599.0	-12,142,676.0	2,954,918.0	6,442,223.0	52,005,006.0	599,966.0	59.4	62,905,451.0
Champ ion B. Plc	2013	9,137,716.0	13,683,275.0	1,058,062.0	-933,273.0	-0.0	-1,178,025.0	4,608,386.0	900,000.0	16.9	2,233,259.0
Champ ion B. Plc	2014	9,592,381.0	3,578,929.0	1,008,118.0	-277,159.0	-313,807.0	-754,523.0	5,870,431.0	7,200,000.0	7.0	3,302,383.0
Champ ion B. Plc	2015	10,329,160.0	3,073,998.0	1,287,183.0	-653,727.0	-0.0	77,140.0	7,121,637.0	7,829,496.0	3.4	3,501,845.0

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Champ ion B. Plc	2 01 6	9,961, 240.0	2,208 ,173.0	368,01 9.0	- 418,57 3.0		530,3 89.0	7,670, 860.0	7,829 ,496. 0		2.5	3,864, 943.0
Champ ion B. Plc	2 01 7	10,08 8,861. 0	1,627, 573.0	47,221. 0	- 855,13 8.0		517,56 2.0	8,135, 460.0	7,829 ,496. 0		2.1	4,777, 313.0
Champ ion B. Plc	2 01 8	10,48 7,010. 0	2,305 ,491. 0	1,142,4 54.0	- 1,267,8 56.0		- 263,8 07.0	7,935, 532.0	7,829 ,496. 0		2.0	4,763, 757.0
Champ ion B. Plc	2 01 9	10,981 ,383.0	2,564 ,456. 0	1,637,0 27.0	- 1,120,9 54.0		168,5 08.0	8,031, 796.0	7,829 ,496. 0		1.0	6,927, 177.0
Champ ion B. Plc	2 0 2	11,368 ,517.0	2,251, 657.0	1,976,0 64.0	- 1,620, 959.0	- 31,826. 0	158,79 3.0	8,042 ,994. 0	7,829 ,496. 0		0.9	7,051, 806.0
Champ ion B. Plc	2 0 21	13,48 6,815. 0	3,435 ,750. 0	3,759,3 96.0	- 1,833,5 81.0	- 79,022. 0	984,2 33.0	9,219, 643.0	7,829 ,496. 0		2.4	10,518 ,497.0
Champ ion B. Plc	2 0 2	15,453 ,585.0	2,926 ,961. 0	2,260,1 74.0	- 2,851,1 21.0	- 92,272. 0	1,585, 978.0	11,119 ,384. 0	7,829 ,496. 0		5.5	12,288 ,893.0
Champ ion B. Plc	2 0 3	20,53 3,079. 0	7,968 ,406. 0	5,822,7 57.0	- 6,581, 822.0	1,014,8 75.0	370,5 63.0	11,195 ,299. 0	7,829 ,496. 0		3.6	12,704 ,274.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria

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Company	Year	TA (N'oo o)	CL (N'oo o)	NCFO (N'oo o)	NCFI (N'oo o)	NCFE (N'oo o)	PAT (N'oo o)	TE (N'oo o)	ESO (Unit)	MP (N)	REV (N'oo o)
BUA Cement Plc	2013	15,058,476.0	4,101,944.0	2,071,903.0	1,157,105.0	439,656.0	1,559,031.0	8,284,619.0	1,256,678.0	11.8	15,311,004.0
BUA Cement Plc	2014	15,780,013.0	3,496,155.0	1,863,994.0	1,786,509.0	258,179.0	1,918,362.0	9,445,658.0	1,256,678.0	10.4	15,119,051.0
BUA Cement Plc	2015	17,146,883.0	4,145,323.0	2,569,229.0	2,260,421.0	223,636.0	1,201,108.0	10,144,768.0	1,256,678.0	9.4	13,037,847.0
BUA Cement Plc	2016	20,030,222.0	5,501,981.0	2,799,490.0	980,194.0	360,490.0	1,253,805.0	11,493,272.0	1,256,678.0	4.8	14,087,553.0
BUA Cement Plc	2017	24,648,676.0	7,165,954.0	3,625,888.0	2,571,250.0	384,459.0	3,223,854.0	14,412,207.0	1,256,678.0	9.5	19,588,261.0
BUA Cement Plc	2018	347,746,456.0	11,554,244.0	1,362,117.0	2,733,048.0	166,894.0	5,731,321.0	333,487,688.0	13,143,502.0	19.4	31,721,962.0
BUA Cement Plc	2019	356,753,843.0	13,448,729.0	10,964,758.0	6,717,917.0	204,265.0	7,283,413.0	340,771,502.0	13,143,502.0	18.1	32,148,368.0
BUA Cement Plc	2020	766,302,578.0	208,100,189.0	65,112,598.0	128,849,627.0	1,728,508,889.0	72,344,336.0	375,954,728.0	33,864,354.0	77.4	209,443,487.0

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BUA Cemen t Plc	2 0 21	728,50 7,473. 0	145,35 5,120. 0	198,95 7,257. 0	- 58,07 6,721. 0	- 214,50 3,647. 0	90,07 9,011. 0	398,11 6,748. 0	33,86 4,354 .0	67. 1	257,32 7,091. 0
BUA Cemen t Plc	2 0 22	874,01 1,884. 0	25,756 ,156.0	149,57 3,594. 0	- 102,27 5,234. 0	- 61,628 ,432.0	101,01 0,626. 0	411,112 ,542.0	33,86 4,354 .0	97. 8	360,9 89,105 .0
BUA Cemen t Plc	2 0 23	1,215,6 86,377. 0	377,03 7,627. 0	150,05 2,489. 0	- 104,11 9,517. 0	- 8,005, 350.0	69,45 4,750. 0	385,22 4,150. 0	33,86 4,354 .0	113 .9	459,99 8,999. 0
Cutix Plc	2 0 13	1,073,8 65.0	399,74 4.0	193,53 9.0	- 67,922 .0	- 105,29 1.0	151,42 3.0	597,55 4.0	880, 662.0	1.5	1,929, 477.0
Cutix Plc	2 0 14	1,744,6 70.0	696,15 4.0	126,65 5.0	- 504,9 07.0	- 156,88 2.0	207,11 6.0	699,70 3.0	880, 662.0	1.9	2,234, 959.0
Cutix Plc	2 0 15	1,968, 813.0	922,8 92.0	222,35 5.0	- 217,40 8.0	- 17,784. 0	149,2 09.0	743,71 1.0	880, 662.0	1.8	2,358, 412.0
Cutix Plc	2 0 16	1,891,7 20.0	756,29 7.0	644,99 6.0	- 24,04 5.0	- 563,97 3.0	190,5 51.0	870,21 7.0	880, 662.0	1.4	2,835, 862.0
Cutix Plc	2 0 17	2,329, 792.0	1,112,4 06.0	190,06 8.0	- 45,474 .0	- 108,33 5.0	257,4 97.0	1,013,9 69.0	880, 662.0	0.9	3,675, 712.0
Cutix Plc	2 0 18	2,836, 262.0	1,359, 513.0	609,47 8.0	- 227,57 3.0	- 393,03 1.0	440,2 95.0	1,299, 292.0	880, 662.0	3.0	5,057, 374.0

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Cutix Plc	2019	2,861,339.0	1,032,494.0	427,399.0	197,527.0	221,616.0	477,070.0	1,613,091.0	3,522,664.0	1.9	5,434,107.0
Cutix Plc	2020	3,627,990.0	1,313,836.0	90,130.0	100,166.0	65,044.0	393,053.0	1,805,638.0	3,522,664.0	0.6	5,025,500.0
Cutix Plc	2021	4,801,452.0	2,308,511.0	295,955.0	429,239.0	74,282.0	601,627.0	2,214,333.0	3,522,664.0	1.1	6,745,521.0
Cutix Plc	2022	5,086,471.0	2,109,127.0	1,203,416.0	248,645.0	942,769.0	790,467.0	2,767,160.0	3,522,664.0	2.4	7,852,391.0
Cutix Plc	2023	5,796,790.0	2,332,152.0	514,849.0	263,253.0	258,985.0	792,132.0	3,232,801.0	3,522,664.0	2.3	9,225,071.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2013	821,699.0	150,992,846.0	275,953,727.0	168,619,000.0	-81,589,914.0	210,262,754.0	571,562,826.0	17,040,508.0	219.0	371,551,567.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2014	963,441,064.0	205,829,677.0	195,608,275.0	162,125,000.0	-84,576,991.0	185,814,123.0	638,543,114.0	17,040,508.0	20.0	371,534,117.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2015	1,124,475,000.0	140,586,000.0	249,235,000.0	131,571,000.0	116,052,000.0	213,171,000.0	748,479,000.0	17,040,000.0	170.0	389,215,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2016	1,502,564,000.0	390,226,000.0	236,064,000.0	-75,879,000.0	-112,630,000.0	368,205,000.0	981,367,000.0	17,040,000.0	173.8	426,129,000.0

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						7,000. 0						
Dang. Cem. Plc	2 0 17	1,611,0 87,000 .0	343,95 6,000. 0	297,96 8,000. 0	- 51,278 ,000.0	- 209,73 2,000. 0	254,6 30,00 0.0	991,01 7,000. 0	17,04 0,00 0.0		23 0.0	552,36 4,000. 0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2 0 18	1,721,9 74,000 .0	284,75 9,000. 0	337,18 6,000. 0	- 94,146 ,000.0	- 236,52 8,000. 0	481,4 56,00 0.0	1,293,5 48,00 0.0	17,04 0,00 0.0		18 9.7	618,30 1,000. 0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2 0 19	1,823,9 84,00 0.0	410,57 5,000. 0	333,48 4,000. 0	124,21 9,000. 0	- 262,45 8,000. 0	261,3 49,00 0.0	1,282, 249,00 0.0	17,04 0,00 0.0		142 .0	610,24 7,000. 0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2 0 0	2,116,0 60,00 0.0	538,61 3,000. 0	398,29 0,000. 0	199,33 5,000. 0	- 185,89 4,000. 0	352,6 09,00 0.0	1,352,3 77,000 .0	17,04 0,00 0.0		24 4.9	719,94 5,000. 0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2 0 21	2,582, 298,00 0.0	837,85 8,000. 0	595,74 6,000. 0	170,22 7,000. 0	- 290,55 8,000. 0	381,1 00,00 0.0	1,461,4 72,000 .0	17,04 0,00 0.0		25 7.0	993,39 9,000. 0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2 0 22	2,658, 463,00 0.0	775,84 0,000. 0	364,18 5,000. 0	118,48 5,000. 0	- 380,5 81,000 .0	402,8 57,00 0.0	1,491,5 35,000 .0	17,04 0,00 0.0		261 .0	1,205, 401,00 0.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2 0 23	3,070, 468,00 0.0	1,127,2 36,00 0.0	406,75 9,000. 0	83,78 2,000. 0	- 336,51 7,000. 0	490,3 23,00 0.0	1,602, 964,00 0.0	17,04 0,00 0.0		319 .0	1,297, 639,0 00.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria

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Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2013	87,112,182.0	26,246,090.0	-12,175,509.0	-6,000,000.0	0.0	13,537,612.0	57,125,832.0	12,000.0	11.7	102,467,361.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2014	97,287,804.0	33,220,434.0	-5,595,694.0	-5,200,000.0	0.0	11,908,690.0	51,413,720.0	12,000.0	6.4	94,103,677.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2015	97,287,804.0	34,532,088.0	-10,655,422.0	-3,540,092.0	-4,300,000.0	12,659,855.0	58,526,202.0	12,000.0	6.0	100,092,221.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2016	106,671,333.0	35,516,958.0	-34,548,986.0	-2,109,157.0	-8,500,000.0	14,198,693.0	66,388,057.0	12,000.0	5.9	167,409,161.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2017	198,064,664.0	91,644,487.0	-26,484,287.0	-5,775,419.0	-13,228,332.0	37,822,609.0	99,207,358.0	12,000.0	20.0	198,120,639.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2018	178,523,711.0	66,033,588.0	-7,265,964.0	-2,840,308.0	-15,000,000.0	25,830,941.0	107,180,126.0	12,000.0	15.3	146,549,176.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2019	174,646,907.0	62,487,298.0	-7,751,585.0	-3,566,735.0	-15,000,000.0	12,869,456.0	106,849,582.0	12,000.0	13.6	78,608,142.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2020	259,280,544.0	122,752,272.0	-43,818,395.0	-9,232,795.0	-13,854,483.0	31,370,659.0	125,302,902.0	12,146,878.0	17.6	206,360,656.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2021	349,382,869.0	207,221,431.0	-106,378,342.0	-13,414,678.0	-35,303,840.0	22,660,116.0	129,830,169.0	12,146,878.0	17.4	276,054,781.0

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E-ISSN 3576-4093

Impact Factor: 5.53

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<https://aspjournals.org/ajfir/index.php/ajfir/index>

Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2 0 2 2	490,9 69,83 6.0	305,17 0,514. 0	108,94 6,471.0	- 15,455, 034.0	- 20,889 ,104.0	54,34 6,390. 0	172,0 29,68 5.0	12,14 6,878 .0	16. 1	403,2 45,98 8.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2 0 2 3	601,0 40,52 4.0	518,90 0,557. 0	6,199,7 72.0	- 6,092, 670.0	- 21,474, 246.0	71,99 9,460. 0	81,80 9,910. 0	12,14 6,878 .0	57. 0	441,45 2,953. 0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2 0 13	159,8 66,917 .0	39,334 ,496.0	35,452, 200.0	- 1,235, 097.0	- 22,837 ,480.0	28,02 2,200. 0	92,64 1,665. 0	3,001 ,600. 0	115 .0	97,174 ,505.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2 0 14	343,6 27,55 8.0	36,526 ,476.0	37,737, 758.0	- 33,050 ,495.0	- 23,249 ,783.0	28,36 0,146. 0	276,6 64,33 8.0	4,404 ,176.0	73. 2	105,8 48,65 7.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2 0 15	381,27 2,953. 0	47,557 ,407.0	33,733, 822.0	2,093, 919.0	- 33,412, 891.0	29,83 7,395. 0	302,6 01,86 9.0	4,554 ,902. 0	88. 0	114,55 8,245. 0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2 0 16	537,5 98,21 2.0	112,59 2,247. 0	- 30,907 ,024.0	5,048, 387.0	13,459, 929.0	20,77 8,348. 0	340,0 94,14 3.0	5,480 ,734. 0	38. 9	87,19 8,416. 0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2 0 17	616,16 9,940. 0	282,45 5,768. 0	1,778,5 71.0	- 6,706, 392.0	20,729 ,761.0	13,22 3,626. 0	264,7 68,89 5.0	5,575, 776.0	43. 6	177,17 0,362. 0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2 0 18	577,6 92,29 6.0	173,87 0,677. 0	39,125, 112.0	- 11,801, 206.0	- 40,615 ,290.0	4,141, 764.0	255,7 43,72 5.0	8,673 ,430. 0	12. 5	187,0 43,47 5.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2 0 19	500,0 81,65 3.0	89,216 ,038.0	77,275, 692.0	- 5,918, 974.0	- 39,659 ,029.0	22,721 ,616.0	361,4 21,559 .0	16,10 7,798 .0	15. 3	188,4 07,00 4.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2 0	505,3 32,716 .0	124,52 2,776. 0	48,655 ,540.0	- 6,542, 358.0	- 27,528 ,292.0	28,71 4,884. 0	373,9 74,93 3.0	16,10 7,798 .0	21. 1	202,5 30,35 9.0

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	20											
Lafarge Africa Plc	2021	534,000	133,850	-748,175,715.0	-12,487,697.0	-59,073,388.0	53.450	395.300	16,100	24.00	262,200	
Lafarge Africa Plc	2022	609,182,343.0	169,932,087.0	-91,308,889.0	-19,890,609.0	-10,792,645.0	55.030	434.200	16,100	24.00	340,633,999.0	
Lafarge Africa Plc	2023	689,780,550.0	2,122,659,591.0	147,011,474.0	-32,680,014.0	-63,818,929.0	48.050	450.100	16,100	31.05	372,513,521.0	
Meyer Paint Plc	2013	2,597,517.0	750,754.0	246,381.0	21,541.0	209,268.0	26.149.0	622.382.0	325.000.0	1.40	1,500,112.0	
Meyer Paint Plc	2014	2,435,368.0	690,701.0	140,348.0	16,849.0	213,494.0	33.106.0	581.626.0	325.000.0	0.90	1,340,104.0	
Meyer Paint Plc	2015	2,301,121.0	594,689.0	11,864.0	101.0	110,431.0	73.230.0	638.100.0	291.490.0	0.70	1,187,236.0	
Meyer Paint Plc	2016	2,178,705.0	784,368.0	36,215.0	3,291.0	1,196.0	214.402.0	423.698.0	291.490.0	0.90	1,091,000.0	
Meyer Paint Plc	2017	1,890,966.0	1,273,952.0	20,822.0	24,054.0	58,593.0	267.739.0	302.969.0	497.728.0	0.70	1,097,061.0	
Meyer Paint Plc	2018	1,839,132.0	1,053,881.0	28,336.0	1,831.0	21,642.0	319.297.0	621.063.0	497.728.0	0.60	970,134.0	

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Meyer Paint Plc	2019	3,720,214.0	2,964,620.0	1,949,902.0	-131,402.0	-361,214.0	-13,493.0	607,570.0	497,728.0	0.5	1,106,116.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2020	2,952,080.0	1,272,315.0	2,341,267.0	3,240,078.0	10,047.0	1,108,506.0	1,716,076.0	497,728.0	0.5	827,599.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2021	1,986,513.0	956,666.0	310,230.0	79,002.0	762,108.0	33,673.0	1,003,158.0	497,728.0	0.5	1,118,098.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2022	1,907,674.0	468,779.0	153,867.0	73,173.0	11,484.0	393,617.0	1,396,775.0	497,728.0	2.3	1,435,032.0
Meyer Paint Plc	2023	2,424,767.0	756,395.0	105,719.0	89,675.0	-166.0	235,969.0	1,632,744.0	497,728.0	3.6	2,266,791.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2023 Continued

Company	Year	TA (N'000)	CL (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	TE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)	MP (N)	REV (N'000)
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2013	9,376,225.0	5,212,095.0	1,289,816.0	373,437.0	678,657.0	562,350.0	3,267,313.0	409,500.0	2.8	15,519,856.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2014	11,032,131.0	6,664,532.0	1,635,578.0	123,294.0	1,202,695.0	394,690.0	3,747,004.0	409,500.0	3.0	15,519,856.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2015	11,734,739.0	6,756,676.0	494,129.0	442,487.0	387,001.0	196,640.0	3,802,832.0	982,800.0	4.9	15,155,102.0

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Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2 0 16	13,09 8,732. 0	7,770, 121.0	- 1,557,0 76.0	- 364,78 5.0	1,500,7 67.0	412,3 86.0	4,375 ,223. 0	1,042 ,070. 0		12,189 ,558.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2 0 17	12,974 ,483.0	7,622, 014.0	2,090, 468.0	- 62,00 5.0	- 1,925,3 03.0	190,5 40.0	4,463 ,206. 0	1,042 ,070. 0	2.1	15,921 ,022.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2 0 18	15,156 ,727.0	7,884 ,358. 0	- 167,81 0.0	- 60,195 .0	1,512,7 11.0	486,1 20.0	4,822 ,994. 0	1,042 ,070. 0	2.9	17,612 ,291.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2 0 19	12,358 ,342.0	4,462 ,649. 0	4,837,5 85.0	- 138,81 5.0	- 3,910, 336.0	1,574, 909.0	5,932 ,044. 0	1,250 ,844. 0	3.9	20,33 0,040. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2 0 20	19,80 2,249. 0	7,654, 807.0	4,806, 873.0	- 786,16 7.0	1,678,4 98.0	3,456, 694.0	8,687 ,013. 0	1,250 ,844. 0	6.0	21,521 ,097.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2 0 21	29,69 3,840. 0	15,23 5,021. 0	- 202,86 9.0	514,46 2.0	4,029, 988.0	4,384, 859.0	12,40 1,122. 0	1,250 ,844. 0	17. 1	32,00 7,979. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2 0 22	36,913 ,111.0	20,21 3,120. 0	434,14 6.0	255.47 9.0	307,95 3.0	4,411, 111.0	15,01 3,073 .0	1,250 ,844. 0	21. 0	42,12 8,595. 0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2 0 23	46,67 3,301. 0	29,08 0,166. 0	- 1,793,4 99.0	- 175,26 6.0	4,599, 872.0	3,418, 992.0	16,17 8,032 .0	1,250 ,844. 0	22. 0	47,723 ,375.0
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2 0 13	98,40 2,091. 0	28,21 7,875. 0	8,382, 673.0	783,64 7.0	5,638, 736.0	742,9 03.0	26,55 8,057 .0	1,612 ,066. 0	43. 0	20,23 3,013. 0

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Notore C. Indust. Plc	2 0 14	93,04 7,412. 0	28,76 6,191. 0								
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2 0 15	86,33 3,466. 0	41,29 0,967 .0								
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2 0 16	153,36 3,577. 0	57,78 0,638 .0								
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2 0 17	147,24 3,345. 0	59,83 7,575. 0								
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2 0 18	152,87 5,441. 0	21,73 2,287. 0								
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2 0 19	196,6 27,94 3.0	49,98 8,654 .0								
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2 0 20	220,8 10,05 9.0	52,78 1,677. 0								
Notore C. Indust. Plc	2 0 21	238,9 40,06 4.0	101,0 62,61 0.0								

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Notore C.	20	280,1	88,46		-	-	-	76,10	1,612		32,22
Indust. Plc	22	23,22	7,462.	12,163,	3,015,	7,962,	6,848,	3,166	,066.	62.	6,698.
	22	6.0	0	148.0	550.0	416.0	391.0	.0	0	5	0
Notore C.	20	353,2	141,6		-		-	114,25	43,53	1,612	
Indust. Plc	22	66,96	25,25	2,087,	2,637,	2,536,	1,289.	0,143	,066.	62.	21,545
	23	8.0	7.0	330.0	565.0	439.0	0	.0	0	5	,162.0
CAP Plc	20	3,035,	1,684,	1,448,6	18,245	1,276,6	1,416,	1,268	700,		
	13	012.0	573.0	52.0	.0	49.0	795.0	,148.	000.	48.	6,195,
								0	0	5	824.0
CAP Plc	20	3,080,	1,825,	1,340,9	42,304	1,749,9	1,662,	1,180,	700,		
	14	882.0	999.0	56.0	.0	78.0	426.0	573.0	000.	38.	6,987,
								0	0	0	604.0
CAP Plc	20	3,409,	1,833,	261,70	138,76	1,027,	1,739,	1,520	700,		
	15	300.0	838.0	0.0	7.0	010.0	559.0	,133.	000.	37.	7,056,
								0	0	6	876.0
CAP Plc	20	4,915,	2,495,	134,05	60,724	475,65	1,603,	2,283	700,		
	16	999.0	428.0	4.0	.0	3.0	357.0	,490.	000.	30.	6,813,
								0	0	6	984.0
CAP Plc	20	5,013,	2,671,	1,804,6	40,935	1,356,9	1,498,	2,242	700,		
	17	990.0	721.0	82.0	.0	69.0	730.0	,220.	000.	34.	7,113,
								0	0	6	950.0
CAP Plc	20	6,311,	3,375,	1,742,7	163,111	1,930,	2,029,	2,808	700,		
	18	246.0	254.0	87.0	.0	995.0	343.0	,939.	000.	34.	7,670,
								0	0	9	315.0
CAP Plc	20	6,760,	4,069	1,753,0	152,89	1,930,	1,742,	2,521,	700,		
	19	961.0	,187.0	00.0	3.0	995.0	088.0	684.0	000.	24.	8,410,
								0	0	0	650.0
CAP Plc	20	8,526,	4,781,	990,96	137,22	322,89	1,223,	3,744	700,		
	20	076.0	268.0	2.0	6.0	2.0	124.0	,808.	000.	20.	8,876,
								0	0	0	191.0

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	2021	12,115,919.0	7,532,448.0	-1,278,694.0	-395,375.0	-1,502,309.0	1,122,583.0	4,409,788.0	788,260.0	19.5	14,207,818.0
CAP Plc	2022	13,406,204.0	6,470,057.0	1,340,259.0	-540,163.0	388,990.0	2,376,208.0	6,599,601.0	814,748.0	17.8	19,208,470.0
CAP Plc	2023	15,373,521.0	6,906,761.0	3,581,356.0	-327,636.0	2,018,374.0	2,514,737.0	7,969,707.0	814,748.0	20.9	23,890,279.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria

Where TA= Total Assets, CL= Current Liabilities, NCFO= Net Cash Flow from Operation, NCFI= Net Cash Flow from Investment, NCFE= Net Cash Flow from Financing, PAT= Profit after Tax, TE= Total Equity, ESO= Equity Shares Outstanding, MP= Market Price and REV= Revenue

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